

Thesis submitted as partial fulfilment for the degree of
MSc Environment and Resource Management
IVM Institute for Environmental Studies
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

Circular cities: analyzing bottom-up initiatives for making Amsterdam more circular

Supervisors: Prof. dr. Pieter J.H. van Beukering

PhD Candidate Hanna Dijkstra

Student: Evgeniya Elkina (2659284)

Word Count: 14904

Submission date: June 30, 2020

Abstract

With a rapidly growing urban population, cities face numerous challenges among which improper waste management represents a serious concern. For decades, waste management system has been linear converting natural resources into waste through production. Today, this approach is considered inefficient since it causes the environment deterioration and economic loss. A solution lies in the circular economy which promotes little waste generation during the product lifecycle. Amsterdam is one of the cities aiming to implement this approach to tackle waste management problems. While the circular transition is mostly examined from a top-down perspective, bottom-up initiatives having the potential to facilitate this process are often left unstudied. The purpose of this study is to determine the contribution of bottom-up initiatives to Amsterdam's circular transition looking at its environmental, economic, and social aspects as well as at initiatives' commitment to circularity. The study utilizes the survey method followed by a statistical analysis to investigate the role of such initiatives in the enhancement of public awareness, involvement and behavioral change. The content analysis of such initiatives' official documentation and news articles is conducted to assess the environmental and economic impact and to analyze initiatives' mission statements for their commitment to circularity. The research results communicate that bottom-up initiatives mostly succeed to create an economic value and positively affect citizens' involvement. However, the environmental impact and the influence on the public awareness and partly on behavioral change is insignificant due to their small local scale and inconsistency between the declared and actual priorities. Such initiatives might still play a role as trendsetters thereby indirectly tackling waste problem and contributing to Amsterdam's circular transition.

Abbreviations

BSC – Balanced scorecard

BUI – Bottom-up initiative

CE – Circular economy

CO₂-e – CO₂-equivalent

SD – Sustainable development

TBYW – Taste Before You Waste

UN – United Nations

WCED – World Commission on Environment and Development

Table of Contents

ABSTRACT	2
LIST OF FIGURES	5
LIST OF TABLES	6
INTRODUCTION	7
I. BACKGROUND	8
II. THEORETICAL AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	11
1. CIRCULAR ECONOMY	11
1.1. <i>Background and definition</i>	11
1.2. <i>Circular Economy Principles</i>	12
1.3. <i>Circular Cities</i>	13
2. URBAN GOVERNANCE	14
3. THEORETICAL EVALUATION FRAMEWORK	15
4. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK VISUALIZATION	18
III. RESEARCH QUESTIONS	19
IV. METHODOLOGY	20
1. CASE STUDIES	21
1.1. <i>Food waste initiatives</i>	21
1.2. <i>Plastic waste initiatives</i>	22
2. SURVEY	24
3. CONTENT ANALYSIS	26
V. RESULTS	28
1.1 ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT: CLOSING LOOPS AND RESOURCE COOPERATION (INPUT)	29
1.2 ECONOMIC IMPACT: CLOSING LOOPS AND RESOURCE COOPERATION (INPUT)	32
1.3 SOCIAL IMPACT (AWARENESS AND BEHAVIORAL CHANGE; COMMUNITY)	35
1.4 THE COMMITMENT TO CIRCULARITY	40
VI. DISCUSSION	42
VII. CONCLUSION	47
BIBLIOGRAPHY LIST	48
APPENDICES	58

List of Figures

Figure 1. The 9R Framework.

Figure 2. Framework for measuring the performance of circular BUIs.

Figure 3. Conceptual framework visualization.

Figure 4. Methodology flow.

Figure 5. Age of the respondents.

Figure 6. Income of the respondents.

Figure 7. A dynamic multi-level perspective on technological transition and the assumed role of TBYW, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale and WASTEDlab in it.

List of Tables

Table 1. Dependent and independent variables and assumed causal inference of the study.

Table 2. Step-by-step process of content analysis conduction.

Table 3. Operationalization of the variables.

Table 4. Summary of the environmental impact of TBYW, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale, WASTEDlab.

Table 5. Summary of the economic impact of TBYW, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale, WASTEDlab.

Table 6. Gender of the respondents.

Table 7. Age of the respondents.

Table 8. Income of the respondents.

Table 9. Percentage of correct answers per group.

Table 10. What respondents relied on while answering the questions.

Table 11. Percentage scores statistically different behavior questions.

Table 12. Summary of the social impact of TBYW, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale, WASTEDlab.

Table 13. Content analysis of TBYW's mission statement.

Table 14. Content analysis of InStock Restaurant's mission statement.

Table 15. Content analysis of Plastic Whale's mission statement.

Table 16. Content analysis of WASTEDlab's mission statement.

Introduction

Nowadays mankind faces numerous challenges, among which overpopulation is one of the acutest (see Chiarelli, 1998; Cafaro & Crist, 2012; Singh et al., 2017). Already in 30 years, the world's rapidly growing population is expected to reach 9.7 billion and 68% of them will live in urban areas (UN, 2019). In Europe, the level of urbanization is even higher and will account for 83.7% in 2050 (European Commission, n.d.). With a growing urban population, cities' environmental footprint also increases as a consequence of meeting citizens' wants and needs. This negative environmental impact is expressed in numerous ways, *inter alia* in municipal waste mismanagement.

In scientific literature, researchers often rank improper waste management among the most serious challenges for cities to deal with (see, f.ex. Abdel-Shafy & Mansour, 2018; Mavropoulos, 2010; Zaman & Lehmann, 2011). This fact can be explained by the multi-faceted nature of this problem which exerts negative influence from a few perspectives. As an environmental issue, waste mismanagement contributes to climate change, air and soil pollution, degradation of ecosystems, etc. Moreover, waste constitutes an economic loss and burden to society, since all the inputs used during the lifecycle of the product are lost when the waste is discarded (European Environment Agency, 2014). The described resource use is characterized as linear which means that raw materials are used to produce goods that are disposed of in a short-term period. Such a traditional "linear" perception of resources has proven to be ineffective (Andrews, 2015; Michelini, et al., 2017) and needs changing.

A solution to the problem described may lie in the application of the circular economy (CE) principles. As opposed to the linear economy, the CE concept promotes reduced consumption, renewable energy, restoration and circularity of product components (ibid.). Moreover, the CE is aligned with sustainable development (SD) "that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own need" (WCED, 1987). Currently, there are already several cities moving towards circularity, among which Amsterdam is considered one of the frontrunners (Circle Economy, 2018; Cramer, 2015). As such, Amsterdam has recently set a goal to become fully circular by 2050 with the help of businesses, institutions and residents. The question arises to what extent particular actors facilitate Amsterdam's transformation towards the CE. As far as public authorities are conventionally responsible for maintenance and modernization of waste management system, there are numerous academic and non-academic studies examining the contribution of the public sector to a CE transition (see Cramer, 2015; Escutia & Lehmann, 2017; Ghosh, 2020; Mcdowall, 2017). The role of the commercial sector is also subject to an investigation for consultancies and academics (Bauwens, 2019; Rizos et al., 2018; van Buren et al., 2016). However,

not enough attention is dedicated to the contribution of the bottom-up initiatives to the CE transition, although they possess a potential for accelerating this process (Hargreaves et al., 2011; Kirchherr et al., 2017; Tukahirwa, 2011). More specifically, bottom-up (or community-based) initiatives are civic action groups “including end users as [...] consumers, [...] co-decision makers, co-creators, and/or co-managers” (Miazzo & Kee, 2014). They tend to fulfill the functions of the public sector when the latter fails to address a problem. The detailed study of the role and contribution of such bottom-up initiatives is considered especially crucial since at present, many studies neglect the social dimensions while examining and applying the CE concept (Kirchherr et al., 2017; Murray et al., 2015). As a result, the exclusion of the social aspect from the CE approach prevents it from being sustainable in the understanding of the WCED.

In order to help fill the stated research gap, this thesis examines the activity of the local bottom-up initiatives tackling excessive waste generation, in particular food and plastic waste, and its consequences in the city of Amsterdam. Understanding the degree of local initiatives’ contribution to city’s circularity is especially important both for policy-makers and for the initiatives themselves. On the one hand, policy-makers can make use of this information to overcome the barriers, such as lack of information and public awareness, to improve the implementation of their CE activities (Ehnert et al., 2018; Prendeville et al., 2017). On the other hand, communication of the success and advantages among such initiatives is essential for enabling the transition towards circularity and for the development of the initiatives themselves (van Buren et al., 2016). For these reasons, it is of importance to understand the extent to which local bottom-up initiatives facilitate the circular transition at the city scale.

I. Background

The problem of waste in the Netherlands is acknowledged and set forth in various documents adopted both at the national and municipal levels. One of the most fundamental legal acts in this relation is the National Raw Material Agreement and signed by more than 180 parties in 2017 (Government of the Netherlands, 2017). This agreement enshrines the intention to make reusable raw materials the basis for the Dutch economy and also distinguishes five value chains, *inter alia* Food and Organic Waste Streams, and Plastics (Municipality of Amsterdam, 2020). These two types of waste were the reason for the adoption of other national acts as well. For example, the Government of the Netherlands enacted Plastics Pact NL 2019-2025 which is supposed to facilitate the circular transition (Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2019). The Netherlands also explicitly

declares the intention to tackle water plastic pollution to achieve plastic-free waterways (Keijzer, 2019).

Regarding the city scale, the City of Amsterdam (2012) issued the “Towards the Amsterdam Circular Economy” report that describes different areas of concern in city’s transition to circularity. These areas included *inter alia* food waste. In addition, the Municipality of Amsterdam (2020) named Food and Organic Waste Streams one of the first three values adopted by the City of Amsterdam as a part of its CE strategy. The Municipality also points out the necessity to stop Amsterdam’s canal pollution, since a large share of plastics still ends up there despite the preventive efforts undertaken in this sphere (Silicon Canals, 2019).

Waste, in particular food and plastic waste, is now in the spotlight of the state and the municipality. These particular types of waste represent two types of cycles recognized by the CE. Food waste is regarded as a part of the bio-cycle, in which biomass after being used returns into the environment. Plastic waste in its turn should remain in closed loops since it belongs to the technocycle containing inorganic materials. Only when these products are kept in closed loops, it is possible to ensure a circular use of such materials and prevent further pollution (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2012).

As a result, dealing with food and plastic waste problems is regarded as an integral part of the circular transition. But what do the food and plastic waste problems look like exactly?

Food waste

“Food waste” stands for the food that is suitable for human consumption but that is thrown away “whether or not after it has been kept beyond its expiry date or left to spoil” (FAO, 2013, p. 9). It constitutes a problem for the Netherlands that is the largest contributor in terms of food waste per capita in the European Union (Hauser, 2017). In 2010, a Dutch resident threw away approximately 48 kg of solid food which equals the amount of 2.5 billion euros (The Netherlands Nutrition Centre Foundation, 2019). Since then, an annual amount of food waste decreased to 34.3 kg which still constitutes a significant loss, also in terms of energy (ibid.). Out of the stated amount, 26.5 kg goes to residual and vegetables, fruit, garden waste. Fighting against this problem, the Government of the Netherlands aims to minimize the amount of food waste and support local initiatives that strive for “closing biomass loops, producing recycled raw materials, and the maximum and multiple valorization of biomass” (Ministries of Infrastructure and Water Management, and Economic Affairs and Climate, 2016, p. 44.).

In Amsterdam, the main treatment ways for household and companies' food waste are incineration and biodigestion accordingly that together proceed 97% of all generated food waste (Cramer, 2017; REPAiR, 2018). In 2019, at least 86 kg of household food waste went to residual waste later used for heat production (Municipality of Amsterdam, 2020). Since incineration and biodigestion correspond to the linear economy principles such as “recovery” and “recycling” accordingly, these ways of treatment are considered inefficient from the CE perspective (REPAiR, 2018; Sperl, 2016). Hence, another approach should be applied for tackling food waste. According to C40 (2018), there is need for scaling up initiatives that would enable a high-value reuse of biomass.

Plastic waste

In the Netherlands, the total plastic packaging waste generated has been steadily growing since 2011 and accounted for 29.89 kg per person in 2017 (Statista, 2020). At the county level, the total plastic packaging recycling rate slowly increased from 42% in 2012 up to 52% in 2018 (Afvalfonds Verpakkingen, n.d. - a; Rijksoverheid, 2016). However, there is still much room for improvement (Rijksoverheid, 2016), since plastic waste has the lowest recycling rate in comparison with other types of waste nowadays (Afvalfonds Verpakkingen, n.d - a). When inappropriately treated, plastic may enter the branched system of Dutch waterways and end up in the ocean contributing to the global problem of so-called plastic soup (Leslie et al., 2017).

With an increasing plastic waste generation, the amount plastic separately collected constituted only 2% of all collected waste in Amsterdam in 2013. In the same year, 2.45% of all plastic generated in Amsterdam was collected and possibly recycled (European Commission, 2015 - a). At the same time, the collection does not guarantee full recycling of the waste, some of the plastic together with paper and metal “may be treated abroad” (ibid., p. 6). In 2015, the plastic packaging recycling rate in Amsterdam equaled 7.5% (Gemeente Amsterdam, 2015). In the certain Amsterdam areas, Noord, around 4.5% of plastic waste was collected or recycled, the rest accounting for 448 850 kg was not treated in any way (CITIES Foundation, 2015). Such waste is most likely to end up in a landfill or in nature breaking down to microplastics, contaminating the environment, e.g. Amsterdam's canals (Leslie et al., 2017) and threatening human's and animals' health.

II. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

1. Circular Economy

The CE concept promotes the restoration of any damage done in resource acquisition and stimulates little waste generation during the product lifecycle (Murray et al., 2015). CE is opposed to a linear economy which, on the contrary, implies the conversion of natural resources into waste via production. A linear economy is currently perceived as inefficient since it leads to the environment deterioration and economic loss (Andrews, 2015; Michelini, et al., 2017; Murray et al., 2015).

1.1. Background and definition

The roots of this concept can be tracked down in different theories of environmental and ecological economics, industrial ecology (Murray et al., 2015). The understanding of CE differs across regions: in China, it includes a broader scope of concerns besides waste and resource problems, while in Europe focuses mostly on waste, natural resources, and business opportunities (Kemp & Domenech, 2017). A widespread but differing application of CE may be explained by the uncertainty regarding the origin of the term. For example, Liu et al. (2009) and Yuan et al. (2006) argue that “CE” first appeared in the works of Chinese scientists while Greyson (2009) and Peace & Turner (1990) state that “CE” was originally used in the western literature. So, there are long-lasting scientific debates resulted in the proliferation of definitions mostly overlapping in a common understanding of CE as of “cyclical closed-loop system” (Murray et al., 2015, p.10)

Kirchherr et al. (2017) summarized various understandings of the term “CE” and found that 98% of the examined works do not consider the multi-faceted nature of CE and problems to be solved by it. In particular, the main goal of CE is to achieve SD in forms of economic prosperity, environmental quality and social equity (Ferreira & Fuso-Nerini, 2019; Ghisellini, 2016; Kirchherr et al., 2017; WSED, 1987), hence the definition should encompass all these dimensions. However, the studies mostly concentrate on describing other perspectives (see Dupont-Inglis, 2015; Lieder & Rashid, 2016; Murray et al., 2017; Stahel, 2013) leaving the social dimension behind. Such neglect of the social aspect prevents the CE concept from being aligned with SD which it pursues. Nevertheless, van Buren et al. (2016) addresses this common scientific inconsistency providing a comprehensive definition of CE which represents a new sustainable economic concept “aiming for the creation of the economic value (the economic value of materials or products increases), the social value (minimization of social value destruction throughout the entire system, such as the prevention of

unhealthy working conditions in the extraction of raw materials and reuse) and the environmental value (resilience of natural resources)” (p.3). Taking into account that the social dimension constitutes the core of bottom-up initiatives studied in this research, the above-stated definition of CE is utilized.

1.2. Circular Economy Principles

The CE principles are crucial for understanding an underlying idea of this concept. Scholars mostly use the principles reflected in the 3R framework: reduce, reuse, recycle (see Brennan et al., 2015; Ghisellini et al., 2016; King et al., 2006; PRC, 2008), however, some studies and official reports utilize the extended version of this framework. According to Kirchherr et al. (2017), only a few researchers apply a new 4R framework favoring a widely-accepted 3R model. Still, scholars continue suggesting the inclusion of new principles to existing frameworks. For instance, Potting et al. (2017) and van Buren et al. (2016) propose the usage of 9Rs that enables capturing more details and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the concept (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The 9R Framework (Kirchherr et al., 2017).

As a rule, the listing order of these core principles depicts the hierarchy of their significance for the reduction of material consumption (Ghisellini et al., 2016). The hierarchy starts with the “Refuse” and “Rethink” principles as the most preferable options and finishes with “Recovery” representing the least efficient linear economy principle (Figure 1).

1.3. Circular Cities

1.3.1. Understanding circular cities

Similarly to the term “CE”, there is no clear definition of a “circular city” which leaves the room for scientific discussions. Common features for a few existing definitions are as follows: circular city implements the core principles of CE across all its functions; in a circular city, the idea of waste is eliminated, assets are kept at their highest level of utility and digital technologies play the role of vital processes enabler (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2015; World Economic Forum, 2018). World Economic Forum (2018) identifies seven CE principles needed for a city to become circular based on Amsterdam’s experience:

- 1) Closed loops with all materials infinitely circulating in a city;
- 2) Reduction of emissions with all the energy received from renewable energy sources;
- 3) Value generation with the help of resources;
- 4) Modular design that increases systems adaptability;
- 5) Innovative business models the presence of which would stimulate the transition from goods possession to services use;
- 6) Region-oriented reverse logistics;
- 7) Upgrade of natural systems with human activities positively affecting this process.

Cities are considered a promising platform for the implementation of CE to achieve the SD and the raw materials transition (Cramer, 2017) due to a number of reasons. Firstly, materials are highly concentrated in cities allowing the effective waste reduction with a “closed loop” thinking. Secondly, city is a focal point for productivity and innovations enabling synergies among businesses, bottom-up initiatives, households and local authorities (Crocchi, 2018). Nevertheless, some scholars criticize the application of CE at the city scale claiming that this approach has “unrealistic”, “unclear”, “narrow” goals (Gregson et al., 2015; Pomponi & Moncaster, 2016). Still, despite the existing academic arguments, the European Union actively urges the Member States to undergo a transition towards CE drawing a special attention *inter alia* to cities (European Commission, 2015 - b).

1.3.2. Amsterdam in Transition to a Circular Economy

Amidst already ongoing discussions about the implementation of the CE on the national and municipal levels, in 2015, the Municipality of Amsterdam officially set forth an aim to pursue a CE at the city scale (City of Amsterdam, 2015). In this agenda, Amsterdam declared its intention to turn fully circular by 2050 thereby becoming the first city in the world to state such an ambition explicitly

(C40, 2018). Besides this goal, Amsterdam indicated two other targets: the achievement of 65% household waste separation rate by 2025 to facilitate recycling and reusing and the achievement of the 50% reduction in the use of primary resources by 2030 (Gemeente Amsterdam, n.d.).

In 2016, the City of Amsterdam launched the Circular Innovation Program supporting the innovative projects that spread the knowledge about CE and add something new to the circular transition (Amsterdam Smart City, n.d.). Among other issues, these projects deal with circular food and organic streams chain, and plastics recycling. One of such plastic waste projects supported by the Municipality of Amsterdam is WASTEDlab aiming to contribute to the circular transition through citizens' engagement (ibid.).

In 2020, the Municipality of Amsterdam adopted four guiding documents setting forth Amsterdam's precise ambitions concerning its circular transition. The first one is Amsterdam Circular 2020-2025 Strategy where the Municipality gives the reasoning for the circular transition. There, the City of Amsterdam also claims to focus on three value chains: food and organic waste; consumer goods; and built environment (Municipality of Amsterdam, 2020). Then, Innovation and Implementation Program 2020-2021 describes the projects that are supposed to shape the CE. These documents are based on the concept created by British economist Kate Raworth and called the Doughnut economics, which formed a basis for the tailor-made advisory report "The Amsterdam Doughnut City" (ibid.). Finally, the document "Monitor" sets forth the rules for the measurement of the degree of Amsterdam's circularity (ibid.).

2. Urban governance

A definition of "urban governance" widely-used in academia was proposed by UN-Habitat (2002) as "the sum of the many ways individuals and institutions, public and private, plan and manage the common affairs of the city [...] It includes formal institutions as well as informal arrangements" (p.14).

The urban governance theory emerged in the 1980s as a response to the rapid sophistication of social relations within cities. Now urban development started taking place in a complex environment in which public, private and social sectors are involved (Edelenbos & van Dijk, 2017). As a result of this change, municipalities lost their "monopoly" for directing the events in the cities and share this duty with recently created networks. In 1992, the importance of citizens' involvement in urban governance was established in the UN action plan "Local Agenda 21" since the engagement of local communities was seen as a condition for achieving SD (Rydin, 2010). Another novelty for

urban governance involved the increased role of participation via self-organizing networks and the occurrence of new forms of governance through collective action such as community-based initiatives within these networks (Edelenbos & van Dijk, 2017). Such a process is often called a bottom-up change which means social innovation such as initiatives and entrepreneurial activities grounded and managed by civil society, NGOs, communities, and businesses (Prendeville et al., 2017). For the purposes of this research, bottom-up or community-based initiatives (BUIs or CBIs) mean civic action groups “including end users as ... consumers, ... co-decision makers, co-creators, and/or co-managers” (Miazzo & Kee, 2014). Often, BUIs aim to solve the problems that the public sector fails to address, as it happens with the problem of food waste in Amsterdam. Knowing that Amsterdam’s food waste is primarily incinerated which is the least-efficient available option in terms of the CE, BUIs step up suggesting their own solution. For instance, being one of such BUIs, Taste Before You Waste (TBYW) collects the food supposed to be wasted at markets and gives it away either for free or applying “pay-as-you-feel” principle (TBYW, 2018).

Murphy (2000) also points out the necessity to shift the emphasis from the top-down to the bottom-up, i.e. “people-centered” approach. The transition to a more sustainable city is possible only if the civil society is involved as one of the major actors in the urban governance (ibid.). Since BUIs often introduce alternative practices into the existing system, they may serve as change actors bringing the community to a more just and sustainable urban reality (Ramos-Mejía & Balanzo, 2018). In many cases, BUIs try to foster such an urban transition by using a “soft power mechanism” of increasing political legitimacy (Ehnert et al., 2018). Applying this mechanism which refers to a non-coercive way to make others share your vision (Stoker, 2011), local initiatives both strengthen the supportive power of coercion and regulation, “hard power”, and compensate the lack of it (Ehnert et al., 2018). As a result, local initiatives can softly stimulate the sustainability transition while benefiting the public sector.

3. Theoretical evaluation framework

Various frameworks have been developed to assess the performance of particular actors contributing to the circular transition. For example, Ferreira & Fusco-Nerini (2019) suggest applying the Circular City Analysis Framework (CCAF) which captures 13 sectors important for a circular transition including the relevant for this study waste sector. This framework represents a holistic tool for assessing city’s circularity, however, it is too broad for the purposes of this research. While the

CCAF gives an overview of the factors influencing city's circularity, the current study is aimed at answering a specific research question on the contribution of BUIs.

Another analytical framework developed by Circle Economy, Fabric TNO & the Municipality of Amsterdam (2016) provides a multi-disciplinary approach mostly taking into account environmental and economic aspects of the transition but neglecting the social dimension. Moreover, similarly to the CCAF, the presented framework examines the circularity at the city scale which is irrelevant for this research.

Finally, Martínez (2016) developed another theoretical evaluation framework focusing precisely on local initiatives in the context of circularity. This framework is based on the balanced scorecard (BSC) framework usually used by businesses to identify the current state of the management control system and its cause-effect relationship (Olve & Sjöstrand, 2006). Martínez (2016) suggests an advanced BSC with the sustainability concept integrated into it. The four perspectives of the framework are aligned with the CE concept and formulated as follows: closing loops, resource cooperation, community, and awareness and behavioral change which are defined by a strategy and shape a mission (ibid.). The interrelation of these perspectives, initiative's strategy and mission is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Framework for measuring the performance of circular BUIs (Martínez, 2016)

“Closing loops” refers to the usage of waste as an input for other processes thereby retaining its highest possible utility and value to the maximum possible extent (Bourguignon, 2016). In Figure 2, “Closing loops” is placed the closest to the mission since this perspective being the part of a strategy strongly influences the ultimate mission of an initiative (Martínez, 2016). Such a special role of this perspective can be explained by the fact that “closed loop” constitutes a core idea behind the CE concept as discussed in Section 1.1.

“Resource cooperation” means an exchange of any necessities from financial resources to information and experience. Martínez (2016) identifies four main ways of resource cooperation that enable the existence and operation of an initiative: input, i.e. waste, finance, education, and media. In particular, the latter component is supposed to positively affect citizens’ awareness and behavior. In its turn, resource exchange is stimulated by the “Closing loops” perspective. For example, if some initiatives possess a rich experience of closing loops, their knowledge becomes a valuable asset that other initiatives would need to improve their activity (van Buren et al., 2016). In this study, the emphasis is put only on waste and education aspects.

“Awareness and behavioral change” represents another crucial element for a successful performance of BUIs. Citizens have to be aware not only of the initiatives themselves but also of the underlying environmental problems. CE demands changes in social practices which can be achieved through the participation in local initiatives’ activity. Hence, raised awareness alone is often not enough, it has to result in behavioral change and increased community involvement (Hasan, 2004; Martínez, 2016).

The “community” perspective plays a special role in particular for neighborhood initiatives since they operate only at the local level and depend on the “neighbors” support. Hasan (2004) ranks the importance of community involvement even higher than the significance of laws and enforcements, that are unable to achieve desired results without this perspective. In total, Martínez (2016) identifies three aspects to be ensured: bringing people together and engaging them, creating inclusiveness of projects, giving something back to the community. In this research, the community involvement is studied in detail.

All perspectives will facilitate the functioning of the initiative only when intertwined and influenced by each other.

4. Conceptual framework visualization

Having discussed the core underlying theories and concepts, it is necessary to summarize the main conceptual underpinnings. The depicted in Figure 3 conceptual framework shows the presumed relationship between such concepts as BUIs and circular city.

Figure 3. Conceptual framework visualization.

The circles on the left part of Figure 3 represent numerous BUIs of a different size but with the common goal to achieve circular Amsterdam. These initiatives are enclosed in a dotted circle which represents a city with still to be closed loops.

There are four perspectives that define initiatives' performance and, hence, the ability to achieve the goal. All of these four perspectives correspond to environmental, economic and social impacts which are constituent elements of the SD concept. Most perspectives can simultaneously contribute to a few SD elements so there is only one common arrow leading from the perspectives to the impacts.

These four perspectives and the components of the SD are embraced by the mission of BUIs. The mission embodied in a mission statement is an important part of achieving the circularity since it has to express initiative's commitment to circular transition and establishes priorities for the pursuit of this goal. So, the aspiration to preserve the environment, enhance the economic activity while actively including the local community has to be an integral part of the mission statement (Martínez, 2016).

Provided the initiatives have the environmental, economic and social impact expressed in the above-mentioned perspectives and enshrine the commitment to circularity in their mission statements, I assume that the activity of circular BUIs facilitates the transition to circularity in Amsterdam.

III. Research questions

Having identified the existing research gap in the sphere of circular transition and having discussed the main theories and concepts underlying the stated problem, I aim to answer the following research question:

How do bottom-up initiatives in Amsterdam contribute to city's transition towards circularity?

To provide a detailed answer to the main research question, I identify four research sub-questions each looking into a specific aspect of the problem. These sub-questions are formulated as follows:

- *What environmental impact do bottom-up initiatives have?*
- *What economic impact do bottom-up initiatives have?*
- *What local social impact do bottom-up initiatives have?*

To answer the societal question, it is necessary to find out whether bottom-up initiatives have positive impact on three indicators: public awareness, behavioral change and public involvement.

The final sub-question regards BUIs' commitment to circularity, namely:

- *How is bottom-up initiatives' commitment to circularity expressed in their mission statements?*

IV. Methodology

Figure 4 presents the methods for answering the research questions. This study utilizes the combination of quantitative and qualitative methods which allows offsetting the weaknesses of each approach.

Figure 4. Methodology flow.

1. Case studies

For this research, I examine the BUIs aiming to tackle food and plastic waste and its consequences in Amsterdam.

The sampling of the initiatives was purposive and based on the following criteria:

- The initiative has been actively operating in Amsterdam at least since 2017;
- The initiative aims to tackle food or plastic waste;
- There are enough available data or such data are possible to obtain to study the impacts from initiative's activity.

The initiatives selected in accordance with the stated criteria are described in the following sub-sections.

1.1. Food waste initiatives

1.1.1. Taste Before You Waste Amsterdam

TBYW is a bottom-up initiative founded in Amsterdam in 2012 to contribute to the solution of the food waste problem. The main objective of TBYW is embodied in the mission statement which is “to reduce consumer food waste by providing citizens with inspiration, knowledge and opportunity for responsible and waste-free consumption” (TBYW, 2019 - b, p.8). This initiative engages with the community by providing still edible products for free or using “pay-as-you-feel” principle which attracts the citizens and lets them asking questions about food (Martínez, 2016). Such a financial policy allows targeting a larger share of the population including the most vulnerable citizens and simultaneously educating them (TBYW, 2019 - b). All products and meals provided are vegetarian or vegan which makes the environmental footprint of this initiative even lesser (TBYW, 2019 - a). Moreover, TBYW is managed by concerned citizens and international students who serve as interns and volunteers and coordinate different projects within the initiative. In total, TBYW (2019 – b) holds six types of activities:

- *Food Cycle Markets* being a weekly grocery market that offers still edible but otherwise to be wasted food. The presence of such a market on the street allows drawing public attention to the problem of food waste and targeting a broader Amsterdam's community;
- *Wasteless Wednesday Dinners* being a weekly event at which all dishes served are cooked out of still edible products collected from grocery stores and markets;
- *Wasteless Culture Monday* consisting of a waste-free dinner and a cultural event such as performances, workshops, discussions, screenings held on a weekly basis;

- *Workshops* weekly organized within other projects or separately from them;
- *Catering* provided for the events of partner organizations. Such activity allows the initiative to strengthen its network and share the experience and knowledge;
- *Conferences* held since 2018. Such a day-long event includes platforms for performances, workshops, discussions on the topic of food waste as well as rescued food.

TBYW is constantly growing and embracing even more volunteers, interns, event participants, and locations. Now, TBYW divisions operate independently in other Dutch cities such as Utrecht, Bussum, The Hague, as well as internationally in Kingston (Canada) and Auckland (New Zealand) (ibid.).

1.1.2. InStock Restaurant Amsterdam

InStock Restaurant was founded in 2014 by four Amsterdam citizens concerned with the problem of food waste resulted from unsold products. Being established as a means to solve this issue, InStock Restaurant aims to “reduce food waste [...] by using products that would otherwise remain unsold [...] and make people value food more” (InStock, n.d. - a). The initiative uses what is considered waste by supermarkets as a valuable input for its activity to cook and sell meals. By doing so, as well as by providing catering services, publishing related news and articles online, and holding events, InStock Restaurant team aims to raise citizens’ awareness about food waste problem and the possibilities of such waste prevention. For example, by 2018, the initiative has published “Instock cooking” and “Circular Chefs” cookbooks which teach the reader food waste prevention techniques and principles of circular cooking accordingly (ibid.).

As it is the case with TBYW, InStock Restaurant started as a local initiative in Amsterdam but by April 2020, it managed to establish its divisions in other cities, namely in The Hague and Utrecht.

1.2. Plastic waste initiatives

1.2.1. Plastic Whale

Plastic Whale is a social enterprise established in 2011 in Amsterdam to combat plastic pollution in local canals (Plastic Whale, 2018). Their mission, however, covers a more global perspective: Plastic Whale aims to “make the world’s waters plastic-free [...] by creating economic value from plastic waste [...] involving as many citizens as possible” (Plastic Whale, n.d.).

Plastic Whale claims to embrace all components of SD exerting an environmental impact while plastic fishing in Amsterdam canals, an economic impact by creating value out of collected plastic waste, and a social impact by educating people.

Initially, the value creation was limited by building boats for plastic fishing but later the idea evolved into the Circular Furniture project launched in 2018. Plastic Whale together with the furniture factory Vera create circular office furniture consisting of the “Whale” boardroom, “Whale tale” chairs, the “Barnacle” lamps, and the “Whale” panel (Plastic Whale, n.d.). The enterprise invests in the project with finance and plastic waste which is turned into granules and fibers. The latter is transformed into PET felt serving as a furniture component; the granules are used to create PET foam plates for boats and tables (Plastic Whale, 2018). Throughout the whole process of the office furniture production, Plastic Whale claims to apply CE principles “reduce, reuse, recycle” (ibid.).

The community is supposed to be educated through plastic fishing activities, educational programs, public clean-up events, and online brochures and videos.

Moving towards the achievement of their mission, Plastic Whale enlarged its operation zone having started to fish for plastic not only in Amsterdam but also in Rotterdam (ibid.).

1.2.2. WASTEDlab

WASTEDlab is a local initiative launched under CITIES Foundation in 2015 to contribute to the solution of the plastic waste problem. The initiative aims to “integrate local community members and actors in giving new value to plastic waste” (CITIES Foundation, 2015, p.1). Initially, WASTEDlab operated only in one area of Amsterdam, namely Amsterdam Noord, since the lowest recycling rates in the city were typical exactly of this district (ibid.).

CITIES Foundation (2015) name the following main types of activities within this initiative:

- The *value creation* from the collected plastic waste. This activity initially implied the production of WASTED Blocks that could be used for various purposes such as a tree planter construction or a bench. Nowadays, the WASTED Blocks serve only for educational needs being an example of how people can create a useful product out of waste. Another form of value creation widely used by WASTEDlab today is its recycling and reward system;
- *A community-driven recycling and reward system* to stimulate the locals to recycle waste and participate in WASTEDlab’s activities. This system is based on a local currency provided to a person in return for waste to be recycled. As soon as a person hands in the

waste, he/she receives WASTED coins that can be exchanged for discounts at local enterprises;

- *Educational events and programs* for the local schools. It is considered important to transfer the knowledge to the younger generation in order to secure the legacy of WASTEDlab. Such events often focus on the history of plastics and overconsumption, the typology of plastics, and plastic processing workshops;
- *Summer schools* for raising people's awareness. These schools have a similar concept as the educational programs for schools with the only difference that a person of any age and background is allowed and welcomed to take part in the activities.

Although WASTEDlab was launched in the district with the lowest recycling rates, it aims to expand its zone of influence. That is why since March 2019, WASTEDlab has also been operating in Amsterdam Zuid (WASTEDlab, n.d.). Moreover, this initiative is constantly expanding its network of own recycling bins thereby incentivizing the population to sort out and hand in their litter exactly to WASTED bins.

2. Survey

Survey is a quantitative research tool for collecting primary data that cannot be gathered otherwise. This research method is considered effective for obtaining information on such topics as attitudes, behaviors, lifestyles (Gideon, 2012). For these reasons, survey is an appropriate method for getting up-to-date data to answer the research question on citizens' awareness, behavioral change, and involvement.

The survey consists of several sections: awareness, behavioral patterns, involvement in environmental activities, demographics.

The awareness section aims to assess respondents' knowledge about food and plastic waste problems in the world. The awareness questions were designed using the statements about the general information on these topics from BUIs' official websites. The same section also deals with respondents' awareness of BUIs' activity. This type of questions is based on Hofmeijer (2017) but adjusted to the case studies of this research and presented as the four-item scale where each item corresponds to one BUI.

The behavior section is divided into the questions aiming to reveal respondents' actual commitment to sustainability in terms of waste and into the questions asking about perceived behavioral changes. These actual commitment questions were inspired by Redman & Redman (2014),

who elaborated on sustainable food and waste behaviors, and were adopted to the specifics of this research. I designed a six-item scale where each item corresponds to respondent's degree of agreement or disagreement with one of eight statements on actual behavioral patterns. The perceived behavioral change was revealed by asking direct questions about adopted eco-habits and a more conscious lifestyle.

The involvement section questions are designed to reveal respondents' perceived engagement in pro-environmental activities. This section is supposed to show whether the BUIs affect the frequency of respondents' participation in sustainability events.

Finally, the demographics section includes the questions about respondents' age, monthly net income, and gender which were added at the end of the survey. The average response time was calculated at 6 minutes.

The target population for the questionnaire is residents of Amsterdam and the people who work, study in Amsterdam or visit it on a regular basis. More specifically, I examine two groups of respondents: the study group, which includes those involved in the activity or aware of these BUIs, and the control group, which consists of citizens who are not actively engaged in or unaware of such initiatives.

Before publishing the survey online, I pre-tested it with test-respondents to avoid wording ambiguity and unclarity. Having incorporated the relevant feedback, I structured the survey using Qualtrics and posted it on the social networks. The final version of the survey questions is attached in the Appendix 1.

To reach the targeted population, I used the social network pages, namely Facebook and LinkedIn. The online form of the survey seems relevant for this study since it allows accessing a unique population that is difficult to reach otherwise (Wright, 2005). Moreover, online questionnaires often enable the communication with individuals who could be hesitant to answer the survey in person (ibid.). So, to reach the study group respondents, I published the survey on the personal Facebook and LinkedIn pages and on the pages of Sustainable Community Amsterdam and Zero Waste Amsterdam on Facebook. To access the control group population, I utilized various non-environmental online communities, such as AmsterdamHelpt and VU International Students.

Finally, I used of the IBM SPSS Statistics 26 to establish whether there is a correlation between independent and dependent variables in the social impact part of the study, namely between the actions of the examined initiatives and positive effect on the social dimension. Some of the independent variables are BUIs' online publications, workshops, events, email newsletters and their closing loops activity. The dependent variables are represented by the raised awareness on the food

and plastic waste problems, increased public involvement and behavioral change towards a more conscious lifestyle. Based on the described variables, eight hypotheses are identified to show the possible causal inference. Null Hypothesis (H0) states that there is no correlation between initiatives' actions and public awareness, involvement and behavioral change. The other seven hypotheses, Hypothesis H1-Hypothesis H7, assume that there is correlation between the activities of the BUIs and some or all dependent variables. Each hypothesis is followed by the corresponding theory describing whether the activities of the initiatives have positive, limited or no significant effect on the social dimension in Amsterdam. The detailed explanation of the variables and causal inference is presented in Table 1 in Appendix 2.

3. Content Analysis

Content analysis represents a method for an information analysis widely applied in different scientific fields. In organization studies, content analysis “is commonly used to assess organizations' social and environmental disclosures” (Milne & Adler, 1999, p. 237). While another method is applied to evaluate the social impact, I still make use of content analysis to identify not only the environmental but also the economic impacts from initiatives' activity. Furthermore, content analysis is used to track BUIs' commitment to the circular transition through the examination of their mission statements. Marquez (2016) and Zahan & Sultuna (2019) claim that organizations can communicate their commitments and goals to external stakeholder using their mission statements. After all, this method is believed to be appropriate for answering the formulated research sub-questions since one of its applications is the objective and systematic description of the manifest and latent communication content (Vourvachis & Woodward, 2015). So, content analysis of the annual impact reports, official websites of the BUIs and their partners, and online news articles on BUIs' economic and environmental impact allows deriving the necessary information. As the basis year for the impact assessment, the year 2018 was chosen. It is the latest available time period since annual reports are mostly published six months after the end of the year in question, i.e. in June. Hence, the reports of 2019 are supposed to be available in June 2020 which is beyond the time limits for data collection in this study.

The content analysis is primarily deductive, i.e. theory-driven but also to a smaller extent inductive, i.e. data-driven. Firstly, for deductive analysis, I identified the themes which are environmental and economic impacts, commitment to circularity, and the theme called “other” where the data-driven codes are placed. Then, I identified the corresponding categories. Codes falling into

each category stand for words or phrases that serve as units of the analysis. The analysis of the collected data provides the knowledge whether the initiatives exert an environmental and/or economic impact and whether their mission statements contain the commitment to Amsterdam’s circular transition. A step-by-step procedure of conducting content analysis is summarized in Table 2 in Appendix 3.

To enable the assessment of the mission statement and of the environmental, economic, and other impacts, it is necessary to operationalize the variables. Operationalization allows measuring and comparing variables between each other. Table 3 contains the operationalization of the variables which also serves as a codebook for the content analysis of the environmental and economic impacts. Although the social impact is not assessed by content analysis, I still included it in Table 3 to show which perspectives correspond to this impact. For the other categories, this table serves as a guideline, their specific codebooks are attached as Appendix 6. A more detailed version of the operationalization table can be found in Appendix 4.

Table 3. Operationalization of the variables.

Type of impact	Relevant perspective	Category of measure	Unit of measure proposed in literature	Unit of measure in this research
Environmental impact	Closing loops	Food waste reduction	Kg of waste being upcycled per week/month/year (Martínez, 2016); amount of resources saved (kg/day) (Marin et al., 2018); amount of reused resources (Owen & Liddell, 2016); Amount of food waste treated (%/total food waste) (Ferreira & Fuso-Nerini, 2019).	Saved food (kg/year)
			Amount (%) of GHG reduction (Croci, 2018)	Quantity of GHG avoided (kgCO ₂ eq/year)
	Resource cooperation (input)	Plastic waste reduction	Amount of resources saved (Marin et al., 2018); amount of recycled resources (Owen & Liddell, 2016)	Gathered plastic (kg/year)
			Quantity of PET-bottles (collected per year)	
Economic impact	Closing loops	Value maximization	Revenue from recycled goods sold (€/month) (Eurocities, 2017); potential value of the material after reuse (€) (ibid.)	(Market) price of the goods (€)
	Resource Cooperation (input)			Price of otherwise to be wasted food or plastic (€)

Social impact	Community	Involvement	Number of actively participating people (Ferreira & Fuso-Nerini, 2019; Martínez, 2016)	In this study, not measured in units
	Awareness and behavioral change	Raised awareness	Number of people attending events (Martínez, 2016)	
		Eco-habits adoption	Number of people who have changed their habits (Martínez, 2016)	
Other	Resource cooperation (knowledge)	Knowledge transfer	Number of meetings established for educational purposes (Martínez, 2016); Number of internal events and dissemination activities about CE (Eurocities, 2017)	Presence of the corresponding codes such as “involving actors”.
	Transition	Regime change	-	Presence of the corresponding codes such as “worldwide”, “internationally”.
Commitment to circularity	Mission	Mission statement	Aspiration to preserve the environment, enhance the economic activity while actively including the local community must be included the mission statement (Martínez, 2016)	Quantity of environmental, economic, social and other impact codes

V. Results

In this section, I measure the environmental, economic and social impacts of BUIs’ activity as well as their commitment to circularity to find out whether the initiatives in question contribute to Amsterdam’s transition to circularity.

The environmental impact of the food waste initiatives in the form of “Closing loops” and “Resource cooperation” perspectives is estimated in kilograms of food prevented from being wasted and avoided CO₂-equivalent (CO₂-e) within one year (see Table 3). Then, the environmental impact from the activity of plastic waste initiatives is calculated in kilograms and PET-bottles collected within one year. The outcome is compared with the negative environmental impact in Amsterdam expressed in an annual amount of food wasted in the municipality, the amount of CO₂-e emissions resulted from such waste, the amount of plastic wasted in wild or incinerated and the amount of PET-bottles that are not recycled.

The economic impact from the activity of the BUIs in the form of the “Closing loops” and “Resource cooperation: input” perspectives is estimated in monetary value in euros (€) of goods created and/or provided by such initiatives as it is shown in Table 3.

The social impact representing the “Awareness and Behavioral change” and “Community” perspectives is measured through the survey and the subsequent statistical analysis.

Finally, BUIs’ commitments to the circular transition are assessed by the content analysis of the initiatives’ mission statement.

1.1 Environmental Impact: Closing loops and Resource cooperation (input)

Food waste

According to the estimations of Wageningen University and Research Centre, the total amount of food waste in the Netherlands throughout the whole food chain constituted from 1 814 to 2 509 kilotons in 2017 (The Netherlands Nutrition Centre Foundation, 2019). This quantity equals 106-147 kg per person with an average of 126.5 kg. Applying this estimation to the population of the Municipality of Amsterdam amounting to 862 965 citizens (CBS, 2020), it is found that on average around 109.2 kilotons of food is wasted each year in this city. This amount causes approximately 207.48 kilotons CO₂-e emissions annually (RMIT University, 2020). Since both TBYW and InStock Restaurant gather the products either from supermarkets or from regular markets and stores, this number needs to be recalculated for the retail and distribution sector only. Mirabella et al. (2014) claim that only 5% of food waste occurs at this stage, while 42% is produced by households, 39% by the food industry, and 14% by the catering services. Hence, in retail and distribution, around 5.46 kilotons of food waste occur in Amsterdam annually which causes 10.37 kilotons CO₂-e.

TBYW: According to the latest annual report published by TBYW Amsterdam (2019), this initiative collected 9 800 kg of food to be wasted from 138 activities it held or took part in in 2018. In 2017, the amount of rescued still edible food accounted for 8 378 kg collected from 116 events which shows an increase in 17% of saved food and in 19% of activities (TBYW, 2018). However, the positive environmental impact from this initiative’s activities was higher in 2016 when 11 280 kg of food was rescued at 211 events.

Based on the latest available result from the initiative’s activity, it is calculated that in 2018, TBYW rescued 0.009% of still edible food out of the total amount thrown away in Amsterdam and 0.179% out of the food wasted in retail and distribution. CO₂-e avoided by rescuing such amount of food is calculated for vegetarian and vegan products. As a result, the amount of CO₂-e avoided by this

initiative is lower than if it included meat and fish products. Using the estimations provided by Clune et al. (2017), 1 kg of non-meat and non-fish products causes around 1.2 kg CO₂-e. As a result, in 2018, TBYW avoided 11 760 kg CO₂-e which equals 0.113% out of all GHGs emitted at this stage.

The end-of-year reports are available from 2016 when TBYW registered as an official foundation after 3.5 years of operating unofficially (TBYW, 2017). With only three annual reports available, it is not possible to conclude about an increasing positive environmental impact from TBYW's activity due to the decreased effectiveness in 2017. In June 2020, the 2019 annual report will be published and will show if there is a positive trend since 2018.

InStock Restaurant: This initiative does not publish annual reports of its activity which prevents the comparison of the results throughout different years. By the end of April 2020, all InStock restaurants collected 926 171 kg of food supposed to be discarded, while in January 2020, this amount equaled 853 914 kg (InStock Restaurant, n.d. - b). At the current rate, InStock Restaurants in Amsterdam, Utrecht, The Hague gather around 24 000 kg of food per month and 288 000 kg per year. InStock Restaurant Amsterdam alone saves approximately 96 000 kg per year avoiding thereby 182 400 kg CO₂-e. Each year, InStock Restaurants collect more still edible products that during the previous year, which can be explained by an increasing number of InStock Restaurants in the Netherlands and by the growing popularity with the local population.

Taking this number as the basis for calculation, it is found that the products rescued by InStock Restaurant Amsterdam account for 1.758% of all food waste generated in retail and distribution in Amsterdam. The share of CO₂-e prevented is also 1.758% since InStock Restaurant is not restricted with vegetarian and vegan dishes only.

Plastic waste

As previously stated, each Dutch citizen generates 29.89 kg of plastic packaging waste within one year (Statista, 2020), which results in the total of 25.79 kilotons of plastics wasted by households in the city of Amsterdam annually. By 2015, the plastic packaging recycling rate in Amsterdam increased up to 7.5% (Gemeente Amsterdam, 2015). So, with such a recycling rate, 1.9 kilotons of plastic are recycled and 23.85 kilotons are incinerated, landfilled or end up in the environment.

Moreover, the consumption of single-use plastic bottles is also high in the Netherlands. In 2017, 650 million big and 750 million small PET-bottles were consumed by Dutch residents (The North Sea Foundation, 2017) which gives approximately 81 PET-bottles per person. So, in

Amsterdam alone, around 69.9 million bottles are consumed annually¹. Fortunately, not all these bottles end up in nature and Amsterdam’s canals. According to The North Sea Foundation (2017), 95% of PET-bottles are returned under the deposit return system in the Netherlands. Assuming that this rate applies to the city of Amsterdam as well, it is found that around 3.5 million PET-bottles end up as waste in incinerators or in the environment annually.

Plastic Whale: This plastic waste initiative does not publish annual reports regularly so it is not possible to compare its environmental impact over the years. Nevertheless, having collected “tons of other waste in Amsterdam’s canals” (B Lab, 2020), Plastic Whale keeps records of PET-bottles exclusively since only this type of waste can be used for a further value creation as part of initiative’s activity. According to the Plastic Whale Foundation Impact Report (2018), with the help of 11 236 engaged people and 2 022 pupils, Plastic Whale gathered 46 225 PET-bottles in 2018. Such an impact constitutes 1.32% of all improperly treated PET-bottles in 2018 solely.

WASTEDlab: This initiative also does not publish annual reports of its activity so it is not possible to compare the results throughout different years. According to CITIES Foundation (2015), during the first year of its activity, WASTEDlab gathered 2 233 kg of plastic waste. By May 2020, the total amount increased up to 14 081 kg (WASTEDlab, n.d.) which gives approximately 2 962 kg per year. This amount of plastic collected accounts for 0.012% of all plastic waste that is not recycled. As a result, it can be seen that the positive environmental impact from the initiative’s activity is steadily growing, although it does not significantly contribute to the circular transition at the city scale.

As a result, none of the initiatives subject to research have a significant positive environmental impact and, hence, do not contribute directly to the circular transition in Amsterdam in this way. The environmental impact of all the initiatives is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of the environmental impact of TBYW, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale, WASTEDlab.

	Food in retail (kg; percentage of the total amount)	CO ₂ -e (kg; percentage of the total amount)	Plastic (kg; percentage of the total amount)	PET-bottles (number of bottles; percentage of the total number)	Impact assessment
Wasted in Amsterdam	5 460 000	10 370 000	23 850 000	3 500 000	
TBYW	9 800 (0.179%)	11 760 (0.113%)			Low

¹ This calculation is based exclusively on the number of Amsterdam residents and does not include the negative impact from the visitors of the city.

InStock Restaurant	96 000 (1.758%)	182 400 (1.758%)			Low
Plastic Whale				46 225 (1.32%)	Low
WASTEDlab			2 962 (0.012%)		Low

1.2 Economic impact: Closing loops and Resource cooperation (input)

TBYW: Since this initiative provides still edible products and dinners for free or using “pay-as-you-feel” principle (TBYW, 2019), there is no fixed price for upcycled food which would represent the value created. Still, the participants of TBYW’s events express how they value the food received in the form of donations. According to TBYW (2019), the average donation per person received at Wasteless Wednesday Dinners and Wasteless Culture Mondays in 2018 equals €5.6 which represents an increase by €1.1 since 2016. In total, TBYW received €25 656 as donations (ibid.) which means that around 4 581 dishes served attained monetary value instead of being thrown away in 2018. Meanwhile, each kilogram of food provided by TBYW at all events received the value of €2.94 at least. According to Stenmarck et al. (2016), the value per kilogram of edible food waste thrown away by the wholesale and retail sector is €2.77. So, the current value of food rescued by TBYW is higher than the value the researchers found. Still, it is necessary to consider that not patrons give a donation, which means that the real price for one kilogram of food and for one dish provided by TBYW is even higher.

InStock Restaurant: This initiative offers meals mostly cooked out of supermarket product surplus, using as input what used to be considered waste (Martínez. 2016). The price of a single InStock Amsterdam dish varies from €3.75 to €11 (InStock, n.d. - c) with an average of €7.11. At the same time, the price of a dish in a multiple-course menu varies from €7.2 to €8.6 which gives an average of €7.76. Moreover, the initiative produces its own beer, namely Pieper Bier and Bammelijes Bier, thereby helping to tackle the problem of potato and bread waste accordingly and creating the value for otherwise to be wasted products; these beers cost €4.2 for a 330-ml bottle. Finally, InStock Restaurant offers InStock Granola, a product made out of brewers’ grains which often go to waste (ibid.); this BUI sells this product at the price €3.75 for a 350-gram bag.

As a result, InStock Restaurant Amsterdam manages not only to create value for still edible food but also to make such a value a few times exceed the cost of food waste in retailing calculated by Stenmarck et al. (2016). Unlike TBYW, InStock Restaurant sets a fixed price for its dishes which

allows the initiative to control the amount of value meals receive and also provides relative independence from the customers' willingness to pay.

Plastic Whale: Initially, this initiative was founded with a goal to build a fishing boat out of plastic waste collected in Amsterdam's canals (Plastic Whale, 2018). By 2020, Plastic Whale has already created high value for plastic waste "fished" from the canals by building a fleet that consists of 11 boats in total; each boat was built using around 8 500 PET-bottles (Plastic Whale, n.d.). In 2018 alone, the initiative produced three boats while it had taken Plastic Whale three years to construct the first boat in the beginning (ibid.). Although the price of a single boat is not officially published, the minimum cost of it can be found by using the monetary value of one PET-bottle as a basis for calculations. So, in the Netherlands, there is a PET-bottle deposit return system that foresees a €0.25 refund for a single PET-bottle which size equals or greater than 0.75 liters (Afvalfonds Verpakkingen, n.d. - b). Using this number, it is found that the boat of Plastic Whale made of recycled plastic should cost as least €2 125 for value maximization to take place. Having studied the local boat market (Boats, n.d.; Boats24, n.d.), it is found that the price of freshwater fishing boats starts from €5 000. So, assuming that the cost of Plastic Whale boats equals even the lowest price on the current boat market, Plastic Whale manages to create the value of plastic retrieved from Amsterdam's canals.

In addition, in 2018, Plastic Whale produced 15 Circular Furniture sets each consisting of the Whale table, eight Whale tail chairs, the Barnacle lamp, and the Whale panel (ibid.). This Furniture is created not only out of Amsterdam's canal plastic but also out of other waste such as steel or residual fabrics (Vepa, n.d.). This fact means that the price given to such a set includes both the value of PET-bottles and other waste streams. In particular, 1004 PET-bottles are used during the production of one boardroom table, 67 PET-bottles for a circular chair, up to 100 plastic bottles for a set of barnacle lamps, and 197 bottles for a single acoustic wall panel (Plastic Whale, 2019). The total price for a Circular Furniture Table and Chair set amounts to €19 800 which is acknowledged to be too high for an average household (Yates, 2018). Such a cost makes the products of Plastic Whale unaffordable for a regular customer, although it also represents a high value created out of plastics and other types of materials thrown away or to be otherwise wasted.

WASTEDlab: The process of the value creation by WASTEDlab differs from the ones that are described above, although a similar procedure was considered initially. In 2015, this BUI aimed to produce WASTED Blocks made mostly of low-density polyethylene (LDPE) and thought to serve for multiple purposes such as a tree planter construction or a bench (CITIES Foundation, 2015). However, the production of WASTED Blocks turned out to be ineffective and the final product

seemed unpractical, so this process was left only as part of educational activities held by WASTEDlab to show the younger generation a way of plastics upcycling (CITIES Foundation, 2015).

Nevertheless, there is a value creation taking place at WASTEDlab which is embodied in Recycling and Reward System. The participants of this program receive WASTED Coins for each bag of waste they bring to a collection point of this initiative; these Coins can be exchanged for a discount at local businesses partnering with WASTEDlab (ibid.). As a result, the value created by this BUI takes the form of a discount that may represent a differing but still monetary value. So, it depends on each particular discount whether the value created surpasses the cost of plastic waste itself. According to the numbers given by WASTEDlab (n.d.), each bag brought by a participant contains approximately 0.8-1.2 kg of plastics. Hence, the discount exchanged for a Coin should exceed the cost of one kilogram of plastic waste which equals €0.60 (Afvalfonds Verpakkingen, n.d. - b).

In conclusion, Plastic Whale has succeeded to create high value out of PET-bottles through the production of the Circular Furniture unsuitable and unaffordable for regular customers, so its economic impact can be assessed as high. InStock Restaurant serves dishes which price a few times exceeds the value of one kilogram of food waste. Still, its economic impact cannot be considered as significant as Plastic Whale's one, even though it multiplies the value of food waste. So, InStock Restaurant's impact is assessed as medium. TBYW creates a food value that exceeds the price given to thrown away food by academia by €0.17. So, there is a particular economic impact, however, it is not significant enough to have any effect, that is way TBYW's impact is assessed as low. Finally, WASTEDlab does not have a fixed value created since it depends on the quantity of discount received by WASTED Reward System participant. As a result, WASTEDlab's economic impact is assessed as "uncertain". These conclusions are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Summary of the economic impact of TBYW, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale, WASTEDlab.

	Value of food waste	Value of plastic waste	Value of PET-bottles	Impact assessment
Academia	1 kg = €2.77	1 kg = €0.60	1 bottle = €0.25	
TBYW	1 kg equals at least €2.94			Low
InStock Restaurant	Average price of one dish is €7.76			Medium
Plastic Whale			Price of Circular Furniture Set is €19 800	High

WASTEDlab		Depends on the discount received		Uncertain
------------------	--	----------------------------------	--	-----------

1.3 Social impact (Awareness and behavioral change; Community)

The total number of survey respondents was 149. To filter valid responses, I paid attention to the time spent completing the survey and to the way responses were given. All respondents who completed the survey in less than two minutes or who chose the same answer category on a long list were removed from the data set. The total number of valid respondents amounts to 125 people. 53 respondents were part of the study group consisting of those involved in the activity or aware of these BUIs. 72 participants were part of the control group containing the people who did not possess much information about the BUIs researched.

As can be seen in Table 6, the absolute majority of the respondents were women and around one fourth of all participants were men.

Table 6. Gender of the respondents.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Male	33	26,4%	26,4%
	Female	91	72,8%	72,8%
	Other	1	0,8%	0,8%
	Total	125	100,0%	100,0%

Almost all respondents were either in the 18-24 age category or in the 25-44 age category (Table 7). Respondent ages are aligned with the targeted population of the BUIs researched and with the demography most representative and active on Facebook where the absolute majority of responses were collected.

Table 7. Age of the respondents.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	18 - 24	63	50,4%	50,4%
	25 - 44	60	48,0%	48,0%
	45 - 64	2	1,6%	1,6%
	Total	125	100,0%	100,0%

Consequently, the monthly net income received by most of the participants was lower than the average in the Netherlands: most of the respondents either earned less than €500 or received from €500 to €1000 per month (Table 8). Moreover, a little share of the participants earned more than €3000 per month. The bar graphs representing the distribution of the age and income of the respondents are attached as Figure 5 and Figure 6 accordingly in Appendix 5.

Table 8. Income of the respondents.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Under 500 €	37	29,6%	29,6%
	500 € – 1000 €	40	32,0%	32,0%
	1000 € – 3000 €	25	20,0%	20,0%
	3000 € – 6000 €	5	4,0%	4,0%
	6000 € – 10000 €	1	0,8%	0,8%
	Prefer not to say	17	13,6%	13,6%
	Total	125	100,0%	100,0%

For the collected data analysis, I used SPSS Statistics 26. To reveal, whether there is a statistically significant difference between the answers given by the study and the control groups to the awareness questions, I compared the means of these two groups with Mann-Whitney test. The degree of the statistical significance was determined by the p-value. Then, I conducted Chi-Square Tests to reveal whether there is statistically significant difference between behavioral habits of the study and control group respondents which is also measured with p-value.

For the awareness section, one out of four awareness questions was found statistically significant at the 1% level, meaning the answer to this question is statistically different between the study and control groups. This question is highlighted in bold in Table 9. The other responses are not statistically different between two groups in questions. However, the share of respondents who answered all questions correctly is 2,5 times higher in the study group than in the control group accounting for 18.8% and 6.9% accordingly.

Table 9. Percentage of correct answers per group.

	STUDY (n=53)	CONTROL (n=72)	p-value
Food waste can occur at different stages of the supply chain. At what stage do you think the most food waste occurs?	45.3%	13.9%	0.010
What food gets thrown away the most?	77.4%	79.1%	0.805
What is the most efficient way to tackle plastic waste?	69.8%	58.3%	0.177
Where does the majority of plastic waste end up?	52.8%	63.9%	0.228
Answered all questions correctly	18.9%	6.9%	-

Moreover, analyzing the follow-up question “*What did you rely on while answering the previous questions?*”, one finds that the respondents of the study group mostly relied on the combination of their knowledge and intuition or on their knowledge solely while the control group respondents mostly used their intuition, the combination of their knowledge and intuition or answered randomly in a few cases (Table 10).

Table 10. What respondents relied on while answering the questions.

	STUDY (n=53)	CONTROL (n=72)
Purely Knowledge	34%	20.8%
Purely Intuition	22.6%	37.5%
Knowledge & Intuition	43.4%	37.5%
Knowledge & Random	0%	1.4%
Knowledge & Intuition & Random	0%	2.8%

Regarding the behavioral change section, the responses to two out of eight behavioral questions were statistically different between the study and the control groups (Table 11). The study group respondents chose food with no or little packaging more often than the control group which is statistically significant at 1% level. Moreover, the study group appeared to find another usage for the plastics left after the products more frequently which is statistically significant at 5% level. The corresponding statements are highlighted in bold in Table 11.

The last question in this section concerned not behavioral patterns but the perception of waste as a problem in Amsterdam. The results of the study and the control groups do not differ statistically significantly which means that this problem is acknowledged among the majority of people of various interests and concerns.

Table 11. Percentage scores statistically different behavior questions.

	STUDY (n=53)				CONTROL (n=72)				p-value
	Agree / somewhat agree	Undecided	Somewhat disagree / Disagree	Not sure / Don't know	Agree / somewhat agree	Undecided	Somewhat disagree / Disagree	Not sure / Don't know	
I buy food in small quantities to avoid its spoiling in my fridge.	92%	3.8%	3.8%	0%	81.9%	9.7%	8.3%	0%	0.237
I throw away the products that seem to have gone bad without tasting and smelling them.	22.6%	5.7%	71.7%	0%	26.4%	11.1%	62.5%	0%	0.451
I repurpose or recycle my food waste when it occurs.	20.8%	15.1%	64.2%	0%	26.5%	12.5%	59.7%	1.4%	0.708
I tend to buy some food spontaneously.	45.5%	22.6%	30.2%	1.9%	50%	31.9%	18.1%	0%	0.223
I choose food with little or no plastic packaging.	66%	17%	17%	0%	33.3%	36.1%	29.2%	1.4%	0.004
I sort out the waste from my household including plastic.	79.2%	7.4%	13.2%	0%	76.4%	4.2%	18.1%	1.4%	0.606
I purchase bottled water.	15.1%	3.8%	81.1%	0%	16.7%	12.5%	69.4%	1.4%	0.263
I find another usage for the plastic left after the products.	30.2%	34%	35.8%	0%	23.6%	15.5%	61.1%	0%	0.011
I believe that waste is an issue in Amsterdam.	92.5%	3.8%	3.8%	0%	80.6%	13.9%	2.8%	2.8%	0.149

Another set of the behavioral change questions asked to the members of the study group showed that 54.7% of such respondents started participating in different environmental events more often since they had learned about one or more of the BUIs. Meanwhile, 41.6% of the study groups respondents indicated no effect on their participation in environmental events and 3.8% did not know whether these initiatives affected their participation in any way.

Answering the question “*In principle, have you started paying more attention to your environmental footprint since you became aware of the initiative(s)?*”, 66% of the study group respondents acknowledged the positive impact of the BUIs on their concern about their environmental footprint. At the same time, 28.3% of the participants reported no observable effect on their paying any more attention to the environmental footprint. The rest did not know the answer to this question or preferred not to respond at all.

Finally, the last question from the behavioral change section concerned the adoption of new environmentally friendly habits after finding out about these BUIs. As a result, 47.2% of the respondents confirmed acquiring new habits such as being more careful about buying and throwing away food, buying zero waste, sorting out the litter and recycling it, etc. Meanwhile, 43.4% of the study group participants did not adopt any new habits and 9.4% responded they did not know.

The last section dealt with all respondents’ intention to participate in the activity of the BUIs studied in any way. The majority of the respondents, 51.2%, would like to receive regular updates from one or a few initiatives to know more about plastic and/or food waste problem. This population may be regarded as a potential target group for the BUIs to attract new participants and subscribers. Then, the share of those unwilling to receive such information from the BUIs accounted for 43.2%, the rest were yet unsure whether they would like to receive such updates.

Lastly, the survey participants were asked whether they would like to make any or more voluntary donations to support the initiative(s) in their activity, in other words, to provide the BUIs with financial support. For this section, multiple answers could be chosen. In total, 70.4% of respondents expressed their willingness to donate unconditionally or under certain circumstances. 39.2% of the participants agreed to contribute financially if they had more money which corresponds to the perception of the financial situation of the population surveyed. Then, 13.7% expressed the readiness to donate if they received more information why it is important which indicates the lack of awareness and understanding of the food and plastic waste problem as such and of the way the BUIs function.

As a result, the BUIs in question succeed to exert a positive influence on the public involvement. However, the awareness of the community involved in the activities of these BUIs is not statistically different from the awareness of those who do not take part in such events. The findings concerning behavioral change are ambiguous since most respondents from the study group acknowledged the positive impact of the BUIs on their behavior, however, the statistical analysis did not show the difference in behavioral patterns between two groups. The social impact of BUIs’ activity is summarized in Table 12.

Table 12. Summary of the social impact of TBYW, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale, WASTEDlab.

Social impact	Impact	Impact assessment
Awareness raising	There is one out of four responses that is statistically different between the study and control groups.	Low
Behavioral change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is two out of eight actual behavioral patterns that are statistically different between the study and control groups. • The relative majority of the study group respondents indicated a positive impact of the BUIs on their behavior. 	Uncertain
Involvement in pro-environmental actions	The absolute majority of the study group respondents claimed that the BUIs had a positive impact on their involvement in pro-environmental activities. However, these statements are only verbal commitments.	Medium

1.4 The commitment to circularity

The content analysis of BUIs’ mission statements was to reveal the commitment of the initiatives to Amsterdam’s circular transition. These mission statements had to contain all three components of the SD that correspond to “closing loops” and “resource cooperation: input”, “awareness and behavioral change”, and “community” perspectives. Since the content analysis was primarily deductive, the codes were found after the theme and category identification while examining the respective mission statements. The frequency of a particular code’s appearance in a mission statement was interpreted as a degree of importance with which a BUI threatens a corresponding dimension. The more often codes of same perspective are mentioned, the more emphasis the BUI claims to put on this perspective.

In the mission statements shown in Appendix 6, none of the initiatives explicitly name the achievement of circularity as their ultimate goal. Nevertheless, all their missions are still aligned with and contribute to a circular transition in Amsterdam to a certain degree since these mission statements include all SD components.

The social dimension is crucial for community-driven organizations and all BUIs refer to it but do so in different ways. The most vivid focus on the societal involvement and awareness is found in TBYW’s statement which mentions the social impact codes significantly more often than the other aspects (Table 13). Similarly, InStock Restaurant seems to prioritize the social impact higher than the

other dimensions. (Table 14). This initiative mostly concentrates on the activities raising public awareness. WASTEDlab also pays more attention to the societal dimension prioritizing public involvement over the other perspectives. Finally, Plastic Whale does not highlight the social impact as its main priority and evenly distributes different perspectives' codes across the mission statement. This finding implies that Plastic Whale treats all dimensions as equally important.

Interestingly, unlike the other initiatives, Plastic Whale and WASTEDlab include the “Resource cooperation: knowledge” perspective in their mission statements. By “involving as many [...] businesses as possible” (Plastic Whale, n.d.; Table 15) and “integrating local [...] actors” (CITIES Foundation, 2015; Table 16), these initiatives are supposed to stimulate the knowledge transfer between them and other actors.

Finally, there is a differential peculiarity found in the mission statement of TBYW and Plastic Whale, namely the strive for exerting a bigger than local impact (Table 13 and Table 15). Being a neighborhood initiative, TBYW aims to “revolutionize the food system” and thereby influence the entire regime of food waste problem (TBYW, 2019 – b, p.8; Table 13). Similarly, Plastic Whale pursues the same goal but regarding the plastic waste regime by achieving “plastic-free waters worldwide” (Plastic Whale, n.d.; Table 15).

As a result, all BUIs pursue circularity in Amsterdam and pay attention to the social dimension. The particular initiatives indicate the goals going beyond the environmental, economic and social impacts on the city scale. Some of them aim to involve other actors thereby allowing for knowledge transfer while others are willing to exert a more global influence rather than city's one.

VI. Discussion

This section looks at the results of this study against other existing scientific findings and reveals questions for further research and particular study limitations.

All BUIs' in question do not significantly contribute to the "closing loops" perspective although it can be considered the most important one from the circular point of view (Martínez, 2016). However, this fact does not mean that the initiatives fail to exert any influence. Selma Seddik, the co-founder of InStock Restaurant, believes that the solution of the food waste problem lies not in the collection of as much food waste as possible but in the inspiration of other people both in the Netherlands and around the world (ibid.). Prilleltensky & Prilleltensky (2006) come to a similar conclusion pointing out the importance of delivering the right idea to other communities. Trendsetting is claimed to be a necessary and desirable aspect of initiatives' activity since such a neighborhood organization operates at a too small scale to be able to reach the population needed for a problem solution. In their study, Prilleltensky & Prilleltensky (2006) draw an example of New Zealand's indigenous group aiming to educate the population about the rights of the indigenous people. Understanding that it is not enough to raise awareness of a reachable population only, this group pursues a strategy of disseminating the information about indigenous people's problems among other organizations. In the case of the BUIs in question, the aim is not only to raise awareness but also to positively change behavior, stimulate community's involvement, combat waste pollution and create economic value. So, even more significance is attached to the process of trendsetting.

Importantly, trendsetting refers not only to the initiative being a role model for other organizations but also to the personal change of initiative's participants and people to whom this idea is accidentally delivered (ibid.). For example, describing fashion industry as a case study, Workman et al. (2017) regards trendsetting only as a process of innovation adoption by individuals and the subsequent innovation communication to others. Still, this process is crucial for cultivating and spreading pro-environmental behavior worldwide to address global environmental problems (ibid).

The idea of combatting the global problems rather than just local ones is explicitly reflected in the mission statements of TBYW and Plastic Whale. This intention is aligned with the urban governance, sustainability transition but also multi-level perspective theories (Bilali, 2019; Geels, 2002; Rip et al., 1998). Concerning this research, BUIs in question represent niches, i.e. micro-level of a possible transition where the idea emerges. Bui et al. (2016) regard niches as initiatives in which differing practices are created and applied by various actors. These initiatives have to be robust enough to challenge the existing regime for a sustainability transition to take place (Bilali, 2019). The regime

itself, i.e. meso-level, often means a conventional sector and its well-established practices and patterns (Bilali, 2019), which in this research refers to the current food and plastic systems.

However, Proka et. al (2018) describes the cases when niches are unwilling to conflict with and, hence, change the existing regime. In the case of renewable energy initiatives, not all of them aim to contribute to the system change, namely to the energy transition. Some initiatives rather prefer to remain local satisfying the local needs of a small community and avoiding conflicts with the regime (Seyfang et al., 2013). This may be the case of WASTEDlab since this BUI does not seem to concentrate on any sustainability transition other than the local one. Regarding InStock Restaurant, this BUI may imply the system change as its goal, however, this assumption results exclusively from the above-mentioned statement of initiative’s co-founder about trendsetting.

Finally, landscape or macro-level represents different external and sometimes international trends and factors affecting the sustainability transformation (Bilali, 2019). This level is not so well-researched in comparison to the other ones allowing for interpretations. In the case of this research, the landscape might refer to the global pollution problem, climate change, consumerism, etc. The main role of the macro-level is thought to result in putting pressure on the regime thereby creating development opportunities for niches (ibid.). The visual representation of the multi-level perspective and the assumed role of the BUIs in it are depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7. A dynamic multi-level perspective on technological transition (Geels, 2002) and the assumed role of TBYW, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale and WASTEDlab in it.

Figure 7 is also demonstrative in terms of showing a possible development pattern of innovations. Over time, a certain share of initiatives fails to sustain their functioning and ceases to exist. To prevent this situation from happening as much as possible, it is important to consider internal niche processes, i.e. interactions within niches (Bilali, 2019). In this relation, Plastic Whale and WASTEDlab mention the involvement of other actors businesses and other actors in their activity which is supposed to stimulate their partnership relations. Moreover, at Dresden Nexus Conference 2020: Circular Economy in a Sustainable Society, different speakers, e.g. Kang (2020) and Lekan (2020), also pointed out the importance of interactions within a micro-level. Lekan (2020) also believes that the communication between initiatives is supposed to facilitate the development of each particular initiative rather than cause a rivalry among them. Such initiatives are situated at different meta-levels so they would be rather willing to collaborate (ibid.). This collaboration would allow the communication of the success and advantages among such initiatives is essential for enabling the transition towards circularity and for the development of the initiatives themselves (van Buren et al., 2016).

Another problem touched upon at Dresden Nexus Conference 2020 is the proliferation of recycling initiatives. Anne van Bruggen, Sustainability and CE Researcher at the Dutch Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM), claimed during the debates that in the Netherlands, the “activities in CE [...] are generally focused on increasing recycling... and less on rethinking and reducing”. Most of the BUIs in question seem to represent the minority that does not correspond to this “general” rule. TBYW and InStock Restaurant close loops and create economic value through the process of either food upcycling or reusing. Besides that, these food waste initiatives aspire to educate the people on the ways of food waste prevention and reduction. According to the food waste hierarchy described by Gunasekaran et al. (2020), TBYW and InStock Restaurant manage food waste in two most preferable ways: they prevent food waste and use it for human nutrition thereby valorizing it. Plastic Whale also maximizes the value through the upcycling of PET-bottles thereby increasing their functionality. As for WASTEDlab, the initial product of this initiative, WASTED Blocks, was regarded as unpractical and ineffective, so in this case, one can speak about a downcycling process. At the same time, recycling is considered a part of the linear economy (see Figure 1), that is why the emphasis should be shifted to more circular activities such as reusing, rethinking, etc. Nevertheless, both Plastic Whale and WASTEDlab address the plastic waste problem from the educational perspective thereby indirectly contributing to waste reduction, prevention, etc.

But do, in the end, these enlightenment activities raise public awareness, incentivize people to change their behavior in favor of more environmentally friendly and nudge them to be more

involved in pro-environmental activities? Since the results show that the BUIs researched do not affect awareness and arguably have no significant influence on behavioral change, it may seem that in general, BUIs' impact on the social dimension is relatively low. However, other studies on initiatives' social impact show different results. For example, Hofmeijer (2017) finds that the case study organization tackling marine plastic pollution indeed has a positive impact on the awareness and behavioral change of its participants with a 99% level of confidence. On the contrary, according to the findings of Gotoh (2015), two out of three BUIs dealing with the improvement of private voluntary standards for sustainability showed an inability to transfer the knowledge sufficiently. At the same time, all case studies facilitate community involvement to a different extent (ibid.).

A possible explanation to a relatively low social impact may lie in the inconsistency between the priorities set in the mission statements of some initiatives and the actual goals pursued by these BUIs. Although the content analysis of the missions showed that all BUIs prioritize the social dimension above or at least the same as the other aspects, initiatives' representatives name other priorities as the most important ones. Surprisingly, TBYW and InStock Restaurant name the environmental and economic impact accordingly as the most significant goal of their activity (Martínez, 2016). Moreover, InStock Restaurant called the social dimension as the least important out of all provided options (ibid.). So, the priorities set in the mission statements of these particular initiatives are not representative for their actual targets.

After all, to validate the findings of this research, it is necessary to exclude the limitations existing during this research.

Limitations and recommendation for further research

Firstly, the constrains for this research, mostly connected with the time restrictions but also with the COVID-19 outbreak and the following crisis, influenced the quantity of the BUIs studied. Although four BUIs were examined as the case studies, the actual number of local circular initiatives operating in Amsterdam is not known. The time and thesis volume restrictions also affected the choice of sub-perspectives that were subject to study. In the "Resource cooperation" perspective, the media and financial aspects were fully omitted. In the "Community" perspective, the inclusiveness, i.e. social diversity, of the projects was not considered.

Secondly, position of the "Resource cooperation" perspective in the conceptual framework also raised questions throughout the research. Some forms of this perspective do not directly fall into the SD elements. For example, knowledge transfer as part of this perspective can be attributed either indirectly to all SD components or to neither of them. In this study, I classified knowledge transfer

into a separate category “other” which does not communicate the particular role of this sub-perspective, though. The “Regime change” perspective revealed during the inductive content analysis is also placed in this category since it could not be attributed to the SD elements. It can also be regarded as a part of the circular transition, however, this perspective refers to a more global scale rather than the city one which is not embraced by Figure 2. After all, the developed conceptual framework reflects the general trend and encompasses the majority of perspectives but it still needs further development and validation to include all essential elements.

Thirdly, the survey sample size is considered relatively small. There are some changes in the results possible if the survey covers a larger population. Due to the COVID-19 crisis, the case studies of this research were unable to contribute to the data collection and provide access to their participants, so the search for the study group respondents was manual.

Fourthly, not all case studies were transparent enough. Although transparency is a crucial element of any BUIs (Gotoh, 2015), some of the initiatives researched do not provide regular annual reports reflecting their performance. This issue also affects the accountability of the initiatives since it is not always possible to track down their activities. It could be an interesting question for further research, namely how the lack of transparency and/or accountability influences the social dimension of the BUIs, for example, trust in BUIs or participation in their activities.

Another promising area for research could be the crisis resistance of BUIs. Due to the COVID-19 outbreak followed by the national lockdown in the Netherlands, the BUIs had to face certain difficulties. For example, InStock Restaurant was not able to sustain two out of its three restaurants and had to close them for good (InStock Restaurant, 2020). On the one hand, in comparison with TBYW, InStock Restaurant had created more value and generated bigger income but still was not able to afford two restaurants in the Hague and in Utrecht during the crisis. Meanwhile, TBYW exists owing to donations and hence, receives a smaller income but it managed to keep the other restaurants in the Netherlands and abroad functioning. On the other hand, all TBYW restaurants operate independently and draw up separate annual impact reports for each location, so TBYW represents a form of the social franchise (TBYW, 2016). In its turn, InStock Restaurant does not utilize this concept which is where the difference in their resistance to a crisis may lie.

VII. Conclusion

This research provides insights into the contribution of the local bottom-up initiatives to the circular transition in Amsterdam. To understand the extent of this contribution, I chose four initiatives, namely Taste Before You Waste, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale and WASTEDlab, as case studies. I utilized both qualitative and quantitative methods such as content and statistical analysis accordingly to track their environmental, economic, social impacts and commitment to circularity. The findings revealed the following insights.

Firstly, local circular bottom-up initiatives do not have a significant environmental impact on the waste problem in Amsterdam. Mostly, the scale of such local initiatives is too small to affect the situation at the city level. However, a more important effect in relation to the environmental but also the other impacts may lie the inspiration of the community and other initiatives which is called trendsetting. This process helps to spread the influence of the initiatives across a larger scale.

Secondly, local bottom-up initiatives have a differing economic impact. The food waste initiatives exert either a low or medium influence on the process of value creation. Meanwhile, one plastic waste initiative succeeds in creating a high value of waste collected thereby contributing to a circular transition. Another plastic waste case study has an uncertain economic impact due to a varying per each situation value. Nevertheless, the majority of the local bottom-up initiatives represent a positive trend in the process of circular transition since they do not concentrate on recycling but focus on reusing and upcycling while creating the value.

Thirdly, the case studies show ambiguous results regarding their social impact. The local circular initiatives have no significant positive effect on the public awareness but succeed to increase the public involvement in pro-environmental activities. According to the statistical analysis, there is no significant impact on behavioral patterns, although the respondents claim the opposite.

Finally, the content analysis of initiatives' mission statements reveals that all case studies prioritize the social dimension above or at least the same as the other aspects. However, the actual goals differ from the declared priorities in two out of four case studies. Such an inconsistency between the stated and actual goals may result in an arguably low social impact.

In conclusion, local circular bottom-up initiatives contribute to the circular transition in Amsterdam both directly and indirectly. On the one hand, through their events, local bottom-up initiatives stimulate public involvement and arguably behavioral change; most of them also create and maximize value of waste. On the other hand, they serve as example for other initiatives and citizens inspiring them to take action against waste pollution in the city.

Bibliography list

- Abdel-Shafy, H. I., & Mansour, M. S. (2018). Solid waste issue: Sources, composition, disposal, recycling, and valorization. *Egyptian Journal of Petroleum*, 27(4), 1275–1290. doi: 10.1016/j.ejpe.2018.07.003
- Afvalfonds Verpakkingen. (n.d. - a). Afvalfonds Verpakkingen. *Afvalfonds Verpakkingen*. Retrieved from <https://afvalfondsverpakkingen.nl/en/packaging-waste-fund>
- Afvalfonds Verpakkingen. (n.d. - b). Packaging Waste Management Contribution. *Afvalfonds Verpakkingen*. Retrieved from <https://afvalfondsverpakkingen.nl/en/packaging-waste-management-contribution>
- Amsterdam Smart City. (n.d.) Circular Amsterdam. *Amsterdam Smart City*. Retrieved from <https://amsterdamsmartcity.com/circularamsterdam>
- Andrews, D. (2015). The circular economy, design thinking and education for sustainability. *Local Economy: The Journal of the Local Economy Policy Unit*, 30(3), 305–315. doi: 10.1177/0269094215578226
- B Lab. (2020). B Impact Report: Plastic Whale. *B Corporation*. Retrieved from <https://bcorporation.eu/directory/plastic-whale>
- Bauwens, T., Mees, R., Gerardts, M., Dune, J., Friedl, H., Daniels, C., Teurlings, C., Brasz, M., Henry, M., Hekkert, M.P. & Kirchherr, J. (2019). Disruptors: How Circular Start-ups Can Accelerate the Circular Economy Transition. *Utrecht University*. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338917824_Disruptors_How_Circular_Start-ups_Can_Accelerate_the_Circular_Economy_Transition
- Becker, S., Franke, F., & Gläsel, A. (2018). Regime pressures and organizational forms of community-based sustainability initiatives. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 29, 5–16. doi: 10.1016/j.eist.2017.10.004
- Bilali, H. E. (2019). The Multi-Level Perspective in Research on Sustainability Transitions in Agriculture and Food Systems: A Systematic Review. *Agriculture*, 9(4), 74. doi:10.3390/agriculture9040074
- Boats. (n.d.). The largest global search engine in the leisure marine market with more than 120,000 boats from 146 countries. *Boats*. Retrieved May 1, 2020 from <https://nl.boats.com>
- Boats24. (n.d.). The Ultimate Platform for Advertising Boats and Yachts for Sale: Netherlands. *Boats24*. Retrieved May 1, 2020 from <https://www.boats24.com/boats/#land=c25>
- Bourguignon, D. (2016). Closing the Loop. New Circular Economy Package. *European Parliament*. Retrieved from [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2016/573899/EPRS_BRI\(2016\)573899_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2016/573899/EPRS_BRI(2016)573899_EN.pdf)

- Brennan, G., Tennant, M. & Blomsma, F. (2015). Business and production solutions: closing loops and the circular economy. In: Koppina, H., Blewitt, J. (Eds.), *Sustainability: Key Issues*.
- Bui S.; Cardona A.; Lamine C.; Cerf M. Sustainability transitions: Insights on processes of niche-regime interaction and regime reconfiguration in agri-food systems. *J. Rural Stud.* 2016, 48, 92-103.
- Buren, N. V., Demmers, M., Heijden, R. V. D., & Witlox, F. (2016). Towards a Circular Economy: The Role of Dutch Logistics Industries and Governments. *Sustainability*, 8(7), 647. doi: 10.3390/su8070647
- C40. (2018). Amsterdam's Circular Economy Roadmap: Lessons Learned and Tool for Upscaling. *C40*. Retrieved from https://www.c40.org/case_studies/amsterdam-s-circular-economy-roadmap-lessons-learned-and-tools-for-upscaling
- Cafaro, P., & Crist, E. (2012). *Life on the brink: environmentalists confront overpopulation*. Athens, GA: University of Georgia Press.
- CBS. (2020). Bevolkingsontwikkeling; regio per maand. *Open Data CBS*. Retrieved from: <https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/#/CBS/nl/dataset/37230ned/table?fromstatweb>
- Chiarelli, B. (1998). Overpopulation and the threat of ecological disaster: The need for global bioethics. *The Mankind Quarterly*, 39(2), 225-230.
- Circle Economy, Fabric TNO, & Gemeente Amsterdam. (2016). *Circular Amsterdam. A vision and action agenda for the city and metropolitan area*. Amsterdam.
- Circle Economy. (2018). Amsterdam's pioneering journey to become 100% circular by 2050. *Circle Economy*. Retrieved from <https://www.circle-economy.com/news/amsterdams-pioneering-journey-to-become-100-circular-by-2050>
- CITIES Foundation. (2015). WASTED Pilot Public Report. *CITIES Foundation*. Retrieved from <https://issuu.com/citiesthemagazine/docs/wasted-pilot-public-report>
- City of Amsterdam. (2012). Towards the Amsterdam Circular Economy. *Amsterdam*. Retrieved from www.amsterdam.nl/duurzaam
- City of Amsterdam. (2015). Sustainable Amsterdam. Agenda for renewable energy, clean air, a circular economy and climate resilient city. *Amsterdam*. Retrieved from <https://www.amsterdam.nl/bestuur-organisatie/organisatie/ruimte-economie/ruimte-duurzaamheid/making-amsterdam/sustainability/>
- City of Amsterdam. (n.d.) Policy: Circular Economy. *City of Amsterdam*. Retrieved from <https://www.amsterdam.nl/en/policy/sustainability/circular-economy/>
- Clune, S., Crossin, E., & Verghese, K. (2017). Systematic review of greenhouse gas emissions for different fresh food categories. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 140, 766-783. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.04.082

- Cramer, J. (2015). Moving Towards a Circular Economy in the Netherlands: Challenges and Directions. *Utrecht University*. Retrieved from <https://wp.hum.uu.nl/wp-content/uploads/sites/32/2015/04/Paper-HongKong-JC-april-2014.pdf>
- Cramer, J. (2017). The Raw Materials Transition in the Amsterdam Metropolitan Area: Added Value for the Economy, Well-Being, and the Environment. *Environment: Science and Policy for Sustainable Development*, 59(3), 14-21. doi:10.1080/00139157.2017.1301167
- Croci, E. (2018). Circular cities: setting the agenda. In *Proceedings of the International Conference Circular Cities: Promoting Sustainable Innovation in Urban Systems and Service Within the Energy-Food-Water-Climate Nexus, Milan, Italy* (Vol. 12).
- Edelenbos, J., & van Dijk, M. P. (2017). CHAPTER 1: Introduction: Urban governance in the Realm of Complexity. *Urban Governance in the Realm of Complexity*, 1-22. doi:10.3362/9781780449685.001
- Ehnert, F., Kern, F., Borgström, S., Gorissen, L., Maschmeyer, S., & Egermann, M. (2018). Urban sustainability transitions in a context of multi-level governance: A comparison of four European states. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 26, 101-116. doi:10.1016/j.eist.2017.05.002
- Escutia, E. Z., & Lehmann, M. (2017). Closing loops in Cloud City: Towards Zero-Waste in Aalborg. *Institute of Systems Sciences, Innovation and Sustainability Reports*, 8, 377-401. Retrieved from https://static.uni-graz.at/fileadmin/veranstaltungen/new-business-models/NBM%40Graz2017_Conference_Proceedings.pdf
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2012). Towards the Circular Economy: Economic and Business Rationale for an Accelerated Transition. *Ellen MacArthur Foundation*. Retrieved from <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/assets/downloads/publications/Ellen-MacArthur-Foundation-Towards-the-Circular-Economy-vol.1.pdf>
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2015). *Towards a Circular Economy: Business Rationale for an Accelerated Transition*, s.l.: s.n.
- Elo, S., & Kyngäs, H. (2008). The qualitative content analysis process. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 62, 107-115.
- Eurocities. (2017). *Full Circle. Cities and the Circular Economy*; Eurocities: Brussels, Belgium.
- European Commission. (n.d.). Developments and Forecasts on Continuing Urbanisation. European Commission. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/knowledge4policy/foresight/topic/continuing-urbanisation/developments-and-forecasts-on-continuing-urbanisation_en
- European Commission. (2015 – a.). Capital Factsheet on Separate Collection. *Copenhagen Resource Institute*. Retrieved from <https://www.municipalwasteeurope.eu/sites/default/files/NL%20Amsterdam%20Capital%20factsheet.pdf>

- European Commission. (2015 – b.). *Closing the loop. An EU action plan for the Circular Economy*. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52015DC0614>
- European Environment Agency. (2014). Waste: a Problem or a Resource? *European Environment Agency*. Retrieved from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/signals/signals-2014/articles/waste-a-problem-or-a-resource>
- FAO. (2013). Food Wastage Footprint. Impacts on Natural Resources. *FAO*. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/3/i3347e/i3347e.pdf>
- Ferreira, A. C. D., & Fuso-Nerini, F. (2019). A Framework for Implementing and Tracking Circular Economy in Cities: The Case of Porto. *Sustainability*, 11(6), 1813. doi: 10.3390/su11061813
- Geels, F. W. (2002). Technological transitions as evolutionary reconfiguration processes: A multi-level perspective and a case-study. *Research Policy*, 31(8-9), 1257-1274. doi:10.1016/s0048-7333(02)00062-8
- Gemeente Amsterdam. (2015). Afvalketen in Beeld. Grodstoffen uit Amsterdam. *Amsterdam*. Retrieved from http://mv.sites.macloud.nl/files/2016/01/afvalketen_in_beeld_grondstoffen_uit_amsterdam.pdf
- Gemeente Amsterdam. (n.d.). Amsterdam Circular 2020-2025. *Amsterdam*. Retrieved from https://www.amsterdam.nl/bestuur-organisatie/volg-beleid/ambities/gezonde-duurzame-stad/amsterdam-circulair-2020-2025/#PagCls_15551023
- Ghisellini, P., Cialani, C. & Ulgiati, S. (2016). A review on circular economy: the expected transition to a balanced interplay of environmental and economic systems. *J. Clean. Prod.* 114, 11–32.
- Ghosh, S. K. (2020). *Circular Economy: Global Perspective*. Singapore: Springer Singapore.
- Gideon, L. (2012). The Art of Question Phrasing. *Handbook of Survey Methodology for the Social Sciences*, 91–107. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4614-3876-2_7
- Girard, L. F., & Nocca, F. (2019). Moving Towards the Circular Economy/City Model: Which Tools for Operationalizing This Model? *Sustainability*, 11(22), 6253. doi: 10.3390/su11226253
- Gotoh, Y. (2015). *Bottom-up approaches to private voluntary standards for sustainability in South African agriculture: Improving environmental governance using social learning*. Mater's Project, Utrecht University. Retrieved from https://www.dspace.library.uu.nl/bitstream/handle/2F1874%2F318164%2FMaster%2520Thesis_Yuri%2520Gotoh_Final_4185234.pdf
- Government of the Netherlands. (2017). More Than 180 Signatures for the National Raw Materials Agreement. *Government*. Retrieved from <https://www.government.nl/latest/news/2017/01/25/more-than-180-signatories-for-the-national-raw-materials-agreement>

- Gregson, N., Crang, M., Fuller, S., & Holmes, H. (2015). Interrogating the circular economy: the moral economy of resource recovery in the EU. *Economy and Society*, 44(2), 218–243. doi: 10.1080/03085147.2015.1013353
- Gunasekaran, M., Kavitha, S., Kumar, G., & Banu, R. (2020). *Food Waste to Valuable Resources: Applications and Management*. Academic Press.
- Hargreaves, T., Haxeltine, A., Longhurst, N. & Seyfang, G. (2011). Sustainability transitions from the bottom-up: Civil society, the multi-level perspective and practice theory. Working Paper. *Centre for Social and Economic Research on the Global Environment*. 1-26.
- Hasan, S. E. (2004). Public Awareness Is Key to Successful Waste Management. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part A*, 39(2), 483–492. doi: 10.1081/ese-120027539
- Hauser, E. (2017). Food Waste Statistics. *European Commission*. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/food/sites/food/files/safety/docs/fw_eu-platform_20170331_statistics.pdf
- Hofmeijer, I. (2017). *Achieving Sustainable Development Goal 12: an exploratory study on sustainable consumption in Lima, Peru*. Master's Project, Duke University. Retrieved from <https://dukespace.lib.duke.edu/dspace/handle/10161/14152>
- InStock Restaurant. (2020). We willen minder leuk nieuws met je delen... [E-mail to the author].
- InStock Restaurant. (n.d. - a). Frequently Asked Questions. *Instock*. Retrieved from <https://www.instock.nl/en/qa-frequently-asked-questions-about-instock/>
- InStock Restaurant. (n.d. - b). Homepage. *Instock*. Retrieved from <https://www.instock.nl>
- InStock Restaurant. (n.d. - c). Menukaart. *Instock*. Retrieved from <https://www.instock.nl/app/uploads/2020/06/Menukaart-NL.pdf?x67463>
- Kalmykova, Y., Sadagopan, M., & Rosado, L. (2018). Circular economy – From review of theories and practices to development of implementation tools. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 135, 190–201. doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.10.034
- Kang, H. (2020). *Building inclusive agency networks for community-led actions: From the perspective of transformative capacity in the Eco-capital Suwon, South Korea*. Lecture presented at Dresden Nexus Conference 2020: Circular Economy in a Sustainable Society, Dresden, Germany. Retrieved from https://express.converia.de/frontend/index.php?page_id=14815
- Keijzer, M.C.G. (2019). Missiegedreven Topsectoren en Innovatiebeleid [Letter to Parliament]. Retrieved from <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/kamerstukken/2019/04/26/kamerbrief-over-missiegedreven-topsectoren-en-innovatiebeleid>
- Kemp, R. & Domenech, T. (2017). Circular Economy Policies in China and Europe. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*. 21. doi: 10.1111/jiec.12597.

- King, A. M., Burgess, S. C., Ijomah, W., & McMahon, C. A. (2006). Reducing waste: Repair, recondition, remanufacture or recycle? *Sustainable Development*, 14(4), 257-267. doi:10.1002/sd.271
- Kirchherr, J., Reike, D. & Hekkert, M. (2017). Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 127, 221–232 doi: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.09.005
- Lekan, M. (2020). *At the nexus of bottom-up and top-down approaches to circular economy: circular social enterprise innovations*. Lecture presented at Dresden Nexus Conference 2020: Circular Economy in a Sustainable Society, Dresden, Germany. Retrieved from https://express.converia.de/frontend/index.php?page_id=14815
- Leslie, H., Brandsma, S., Velzen, M. V., & Vethaak, A. (2017). Microplastics en route: Field measurements in the Dutch river delta and Amsterdam canals, wastewater treatment plants, North Sea sediments and biota. *Environment International*, 101, 133–142. doi: 10.1016/j.envint.2017.01.018
- Lin, B. C.-ang., & Zheng, S. (2017). *Environmental economics and sustainability*. Chichester, West Sussex: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Marin, J., & Meulder, B. D. (2018). Interpreting Circularity. Circular City Representations Concealing Transition Drivers. *Sustainability*, 10(5), 1310. doi: 10.3390/su10051310
- Marquez, T. (2016). Words Matter: A Content Analysis Study of Public and Private Higher Education Mission Statements in the Middle States Region. *Education Doctoral*, 286. Retrieved from https://fisherpub.sjfc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1289&context=education_etd
- Martínez, D. S. (2016). *Towards an Inclusive Circular Amsterdam: a Framework for Evaluating Local Circular Initiatives, projects and startups in the city of Amsterdam*. Wageningen University.
- Mavropoulos, A. (2010). Megacities Sustainable Development and Waste Management in the 21st Century. *Hamburg: ISWA Conference*. Retrieved from https://www.iswa.org/uploads/tx_iswaknowledgebase/Mavropoulos.pdf
- Mcdowall, W., Geng, Y., Huang, B., Barteková, E., Bleischwitz, R., Türkeli, S., Miazzo, F., & Kee, T. (2014). *We own the city: enabling community practice in architecture and urban planning*. Amsterdam: Trancity Valiz.
- Michelini, G., Moraes, R. N., Cunha, R. N., Costa, J. M., & Ometto, A. R. (2017). From Linear to Circular Economy: PSS Conducting the Transition. *Procedia CIRP*, 64, 2–6. doi: 10.1016/j.procir.2017.03.012
- Milne, M. J., & Adler, R. W. (1999). Exploring the reliability of social and environmental disclosures content analysis. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 12(2), 237–256. doi: 10.1108/09513579910270138

- Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management. (2019). Plastic Pact NL 2019-2025. *Circulair Ondernemen*. Retrieved from <https://www.circulairondernemen.nl/uploads/0e657a0084a4f18d2ff61335794ea3c7.pdf>
- Mirabella, N., Castellani, V. & Sala, S. (2014). Current options for the valorization of food manufacturing waste: a review. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 65, 28-41.
- Municipality of Amsterdam. (2020). Amsterdam Circular 2020-2025 Strategy. *Gemeente Amsterdam*. Retrieved from <https://www.amsterdam.nl/en/policy/sustainability/circular-economy/>
- Murphy, P. (2000). Urban governance for more sustainable cities. *European Environment: The Journal of European Environmental Policy (Wiley)*, 10(5), 239- 246. Retrieved from <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=bth&AN=9433172&site=ehost-live>
- Murray, A., Skene, K., & Haynes, K. (2015). The Circular Economy: An Interdisciplinary Exploration of the Concept and Application in a Global Context. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 140(3), 369–380. doi: 10.1007/s10551-015-2693-2
- Niven, P. R. (2003). *Balanced scorecard Step-by-step for government and nonprofit agencies*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Olve, N.-G., & Sjöstrand, A. (2006). *Balanced scorecard*. Chichester, GB: Capstone.
- Owen, A., & Liddell, J. (2016). Implementing a Circular Economy at City Scale—a challenge for data and decision making, not technology. *International SEEDS Conference*.
- Plastic Whale Foundation. (2018). Impact Report. *PET Power*. Retrieved from <https://www.petpower.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/Impact-report-2018-PET-Power-2.pdf>
- Plastic Whale. (2018). Brochure: Amsterdam Plastic Fishing. *Plastic Whale*. Retrieved from <https://plasticwhale.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/PW-brochure-EN-webversion.pdf>
- Plastic Whale. (2019). Brochure: Circular Furniture. *Plastic Whale*. Retrieved from <https://plasticwhale.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/PWCF-Brochure-Web.pdf>
- Plastic Whale. (n.d.). Home page. *Plastic Whale*. Retrieved from <https://plasticwhale.com>
- Pomponi, F., & Moncaster, A. (2016). Circular economy for the built environment: A research framework. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 143 710-718. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.12.055>
- Potting, J., Hekkert, M., Worrell, E. & Hanemaaijer, A. (2016). Circular Economy: Measuring innovation in product chains. *PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency*. Retrieved from <http://www.pbl.nl/sites/default/files/cms/publicaties/pbl-2016-circular-economy-measuring-innovation-in-product-chains-2544.pdf>

- PRC. (2008). Circular Economy Promotion Law of the People's Republic of China. *World Bank*. Retrieved from https://ppp.worldbank.org/public-private-partnership/sites/ppp.worldbank.org/files/documents/China_CircularEconomyLawEnglish.pdf.
- Prelims - Urban Governance in the Realm of Complexity. (2017). *Urban Governance in the Realm of Complexity*, i-x. doi: 10.3362/9781780449685.000
- Prilleltensky, I., & Prilleltensky, O. (2006). *Promoting well-being: Linking personal, organizational, and community change*. Hoboken, USA: John Wiley & Sons.
- Proka, A., Hisschemöller, M., & Loorbach, D. (2018). Transition without Conflict? Renewable Energy Initiatives in the Dutch Energy Transition. *Sustainability*, 10(6), 1721. doi:10.3390/su10061721
- Ramos-Mejía, M., & Balanzo, A. (2018). What It Takes to Lead Sustainability Transitions from the Bottom-Up: Strategic Interactions of Grassroots Ecopreneurs. *Sustainability*, 10(7), 2294. doi:10.3390/su10072294
- Redman, E., & Redman, A. (2014). Transforming sustainable food and waste behaviors by realigning domains of knowledge in our education system. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 64, 147-157. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2013.09.016
- REPAiR. (2018). D5.2 Catalogue of solutions and strategies for Amsterdam. *REPAiR*. Retrieved from <http://h2020repair.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/Deliverable-5.2-Catalogue-of-solutions-and-strategies-for-Amsterdam.pdf>
- Rijksoverheid. (2016). A circular economy for the Netherlands by 2050. *Government*. Retrieved from <https://www.government.nl/documents/policy-notes/2016/09/14/a-circular-economy-in-the-netherlands-by-2050>
- Rip, A., Kemp, R. P. M., & Kemp, R. (1998). Technological change. In S. Rayner, & E. L. Malone (Eds.), *Human choice and climate change. Vol. II, Resources and Technology* (pp. 327-399). Columbus, Ohio: Battelle Press.
- RMIT University. (2020). Food Waste Greenhouse Gas Calculator. *Watch My Waste*. Retrieved from <http://watchmywaste.com.au/food-waste-greenhouse-gas-calculator/>
- Rydin, Y. (2010). *Governing for Sustainability. Governing for Sustainable Urban Development, 1*. Routledge.
- Seyfang, G., Park, J.J. & Smith, A. (2013). A thousand flowers blooming? An examination of community energy in the UK. *Energy Policy*, 61, 977-989.
- Silicon Canals. (2019). The Great Bubble Barrier: How This Women-Led Dutch Startup Is Fighting Plastic Pollution. *Silicon Canals*. Retrieved from <https://siliconcanals.com/news/the-great-bubble-barrier-how-this-women-led-dutch-startup-is-fighting-plastic-pollution/>
- Singh, R. P., Singh, A., & Srivastava, V. (2017). *Environmental issues surrounding human overpopulation*. Hershey: Information Science Reference.

- Smit, W. (2018). Urban Governance in Africa: An Overview. *African Cities and the Development Conundrum*. doi: 10.1163/9789004387942_004
- Sperl, L. K. (2016). Innovative Waste Management For a Circular Economy in The Netherlands – Assessing the potential of a multi-stream waste collection system for the city of Amsterdam. *Trier University of Applied Sciences*.
- Statista. (2020). Total plastic packaging waste generated in the Netherlands from 2002 to 2017. *Statista*. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/972801/plastic-packaging-waste-per-capita-in-the-netherlands/>
- Stenmarck, Å., Jensen, C., Quested, T., Moates, G., Buksti, M., Cseh, B., Juul, S., Parry, A., Politano, A., Redlingshofer, B. & Scherhauser, S. (2016). *Estimates of European food waste levels*. IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute.
- Stoker G. (2011), Was Local Governance Such a Good Idea? A Global Comparative Perspective. *Public Administration*, 89: 15-31. doi:10.1111/j.1467-9299.2011.01900.x
- Taste Before You Waste. (2016). Policy Plan 2016-2021. *Amsterdam Taste Before You Waste*. Retrieved from <http://amsterdam.tastebeforeyouwaste.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/PolicyPlanENG.pdf>
- Taste Before You Waste. (2017). Year End Report 2016. *Amsterdam Taste Before You Waste*. Retrieved from https://f56dfd2f-7f3a-42e7-b1db-36b564afe078.filesusr.com/ugd/ca9461_ef961a6a98bd478aa2b1ae21c6e13d2d.pdf
- Taste Before You Waste. (2018). Year End Report 2017. *Amsterdam Taste Before You Waste*. Retrieved from https://f56dfd2f-7f3a-42e7-b1db-36b564afe078.filesusr.com/ugd/ca9461_48444e534cab4596aebec0b7077ee81f.pdf
- Taste Before You Waste. (2019 - a). The Sustainable Future Diet. *Taste Before You Waste*. Retrieved from <https://tastebeforeyouwaste.wixsite.com/mysite-1/post/the-sustainable-future-diet>
- Taste Before You Waste. (2019 - b). Year End Report 2018. *Amsterdam Taste Before You Waste*. Retrieved from https://f56dfd2f-7f3a-42e7-b1db-36b564afe078.filesusr.com/ugd/ca9461_4b4522416b8c48f687e27037dde14e5d.pdf
- The North Sea Foundation. (2017). Bottle Cap Report. *Noordzee*. Retrieved from https://www.noordzee.nl/project/userfiles//SDN_Doppenrapport_EN_2017_DEF_small_2.pdf
- UN-Habitat. (2002). *The Challenges of Slums: Global Report on Human Settlement*. London: Earthscan.
- United Nations. (2019). World Population Prospects 2019: Highlights. *The Population Division of the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs*. Retrieved from https://population.un.org/wpp/Publications/Files/WPP2019_10KeyFindings.pdf

- Van Dooren, C. (2019). Synthesis Report on Food Waste in Dutch Households in 2019. *The Netherlands Nutrition Centre Foundation*. Retrieved from https://mobiel.voedingscentrum.nl/Assets/Uploads/voedingscentrum/Documents/Professionals/Pers/Persmappen/Verspilling%202019/VC_Synthesis%20report%20on%20food%20waste%20in%20Dutch%20households%202019.pdf
- Vepa. (n.d.). Plastic Whale by Vepa. *Vepa*. Retrieved from <https://vepa.nl/plastic-whale-by-vepa/?lang=en>
- Vourvachis, P., & Woodward, T. (2015). Content analysis in social and environmental reporting research: trends and challenges. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 16(2), 166–195. doi: 10.1108/jaar-04-2013-0027
- WASTEDlab. (n.d.). Home page. *Wastedlab*. Retrieved: <https://wastedlab.nl/en/>
- WCED. (1987). Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future. *United Nations*. Retrieved from. <http://www.un-documents.net/our-common-future.pdf>.
- World Bank. (2019). Solid Waste Management. *World Bank*. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/urbandevelopment/brief/solid-waste-management>
- World Economic Forum. (2018). Circular Economy in Cities. Evolving the model for a sustainable urban future. *World Economic Forum*. Retrieved from http://www3.weforum.org/docs/White_paper_Circular_Economy_in_Cities_report_2018.pdf
- Wright, K. B. (2006). Researching Internet-Based Populations: Advantages and Disadvantages of Online Survey Research, Online Questionnaire Authoring Software Packages, and Web Survey Services. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 10(3), 00–00. doi: 10.1111/j.1083-6101.2005.tb00259.x
- Yates, A. (2018). High-End Furniture Made from River Garbage. *Ozy Media*. Retrieved from <https://www.ozy.com/around-the-world/high-end-furniture-made-from-river-garbage/88106/>
- Zahan, M. & Sultana, H. (2019). Sustainable Mission Statement of International Firms: An Empirical Study. *The Jahangirnagar University Journal of Business Research*, 20, 37-51. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337869165_Sustainable_Mission_Statement_of_International_Firms_An_Empirical_Study
- Zaman, A. & Lehmann, S. (2011). Challenges and Opportunities in Transforming a City into a 'Zero Waste City'. *Challenge*. 2.(4) 73-93. doi: 10.3390/challe2040073.

Appendices

Appendix 1. Survey used to test the social impact of the bottom-up initiatives.

The correct answers for the awareness section questions are highlighted with yellow. The bracketed sentences in *italics* were not shown to the respondents and are included here only to allow for the research transparency.

Survey content:

Information on the Survey

Welcome to the survey created as a part of a Master's research project at Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. This questionnaire addresses residents' perception of food and plastic waste in Amsterdam and the possible impact of local community organizations on their own attitude and lifestyle.

This survey will take 5-7 minutes to complete. By participating in this study, you agree to the following:

1. All your data will be treated anonymously. All the answers will be aggregated so that individual answers cannot be traced back to individual respondents;
2. You may quit your participation at any moment during the survey;
3. Please complete the survey in one go. Your participation can benefit only if you read all the questions thoroughly and take them seriously. Your feedback is very important for the study.

If you agree to complete the survey under the stated conditions, please press "Next" button to start the questionnaire.

What is it about?

When the government fails to deal with some problem, communities are prone to step up and form local organizations or so called initiatives to address the issues that they perceive important. With the help of this survey, the researcher aims to understand how residents working, living or visiting Amsterdam frequently perceive the problem of waste in the city and whether the local initiatives fighting against food and plastic waste have an impact on the respondents' attitude and lifestyle.

1. Do you live, work, or study in Amsterdam or visit it on a regular basis?
 - Yes
 - No (*end of the survey*)

Awareness section

The following four questions cover the problem of food and plastic waste in the world. Please answer based on your own opinion and awareness.

2. **Food waste can occur at different stages of the supply chain. At what stage do you think the most food waste occurs?**
 - During transportation

- In supermarkets
- In restaurants and cafes
- In private households

3. What food gets thrown away the most?

- Fruits and vegetables
- Dairy products
- Meat and fish
- Grain products

4. What is the most efficient way to tackle plastic waste:

- Reuse it
- Reduce it
- Recycle it
- Repurpose it

5. Where does the majority of plastic waste end up?

- It is mostly recycled
- Landfills
- The environment and ocean
- Incinerators (sites for burning waste)

6. What did you rely on while answering the previous questions? For this question, multiple answers can be selected.

- Knowledge
 - Intuition
 - Answered randomly
 - Other
- Please specify _____

Behavior patterns section

7. The next section questions you about your particular habits. These sentences are formulated in the first person (e.g. I like strawberries). You will have to agree or disagree with the statements. Please respond honestly. There are no right or wrong answers; your real opinion is important for this research.

	Agree (almost always do it)	Somewhat agree (do it frequently)	Undecided (do it occasionally)	Somewhat disagree (do it rarely)	Disagree (never do it)	Not sure / I don't know
1. I buy food in small quantities to avoid						

its spoiling in my fridge.						
2. I throw away the products that seem to have gone bad without tasting and smelling them.						
3. I repurpose or recycle my food waste when it occurs (e.g. put it in a compost bin/worm farm, etc.).						
4. I tend to buy some food spontaneously.						
5. I choose food with little or no plastic packaging.						
6. I sort out the waste from my household including plastic.						
7. I purchase bottled water (in disposable bottles).						
8. I find another usage for the plastic left after the products (e.g. use plastic bottles as flower pots / use single-use containers for storing small things, etc.).						
9. I believe that waste is an issue in Amsterdam.						

Awareness and involvement section

The next section asks about awareness of and involvement in some Amsterdam local initiatives that aim to tackle food or plastic waste.

- 8. Please, be aware that you should assign each initiative with statement(s) from 1 to 5. If you choose any statement from 2 to 4, please also tick statement 1. If you choose statement 5, it would mean you have not done anything else described in statements 1-4.**

Initiative's name	Taste Before You Waste	InStock Restaurant	Plastic Whale	WASTEDlab
Level of awareness				
1. I have heard of this initiative				
2. I follow this initiative on social media and/or am subscribed for their publications				
3. I have participated in an event of this initiative and/or volunteered for it				
4. I have donated to this initiative at least once				
5. I have NOT heard of this initiative				

9. *(If person belongs to the study group)*

Since you learned about the initiative(s) (Taste Before You Waste, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale, WASTEDlab), have you overall been participating in different environmental events more often?

- Yes
- Probably yes
- Probably no
- No
- I do not know
- Do not want to answer

10. *(If person belongs to the study group)*

In principle, have you started paying more attention to your environmental footprint since you became aware of the initiative(s) (Taste Before You Waste, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale, WASTEDlab)?

- Yes
- Probably yes
- Probably no
- No
- Don't know
- Do not want to answer

11. *(If person belongs to the study group)*

Since you became aware of these initiatives, have you adopted any NEW environment-friendly habits (e.g. sorting out the litter, using less paper, buying plastic-free, etc.)?:

- Yes
Please specify _____
- No
- Don't know

12. **Would you like to make your lifestyle more environmentally friendly? For this question, multiple answers can be selected. *(Multiple choice)***

- Yes
- Probably yes, if it doesn't require much effort from me
- Probably yes, if I find time
- Probably yes, if I get more information on why it is important
- Probably yes, if I get more information on how to do it
- No
- I don't know

13. **In principle, would you like to make any or more voluntary donations to support the initiative(s) (Taste Before You Waste, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale, WASTEDlab) in their activity?**

- Yes
- Probably yes, if I get more information on why it is important
- Probably yes, if I have more money
- No
- I don't know

14. **Would you like to receive regular updates from the initiative(s) (Taste Before You Waste, InStock Restaurant, Plastic Whale, WASTEDlab)?**

- Yes
- Probably yes
- Probably no
- No
- Don't know

15. **Do you know any other local initiatives in Amsterdam that deal with food waste, plastic waste or other environmental problems? Remember, that “local initiatives” are small-scale organizations that operate in a particular area, often involving community activities.**

- No
- Yes (please state the names of such initiatives below if you can recall them)

The next section refers to your awareness of and participation in other environmental organizations. In this section, the size of environmental initiative plays no role, it can be any organization, such as Greenpeace, for example. Please respond honestly. There are no right or wrong answers; your *real* opinion is important for this research.

16. Do you follow other environmental organizations on social media, read environmental blogs, or subscribe to any environmental publication?

- Yes
- No
- Do not want to answer

17. Have you contacted any other environmental organizations to see how you can help?

- Yes
- No
- Do not want to answer

18. Have you participated in events, workshops or conferences specifically concerned with environmental issues other than food and plastic waste?

- Yes, several times a month
- Yes, once a month
- Yes, once in several months
- Yes, several times a year
- Yes, once a year
- No, never
- Don't want to answer

19. (If answer is "NO" to Q17)

Would you like to participate in events, workshops or conferences specifically concerned with environmental issues? (Multiple choice)

- Yes
- Probably yes, if I find the time
- Probably yes, if I get more information
- No
- I do not know
- Do not want to answer

Demographics

Finally, the last set of questions relates to the basic demographics information.

20. Please, indicate to which age group you belong

- 18-24

- 25-44
- 45-64
- 65 and older

21. Please, indicate your gender

- Female
- Male
- Other
- Prefer not to say

22. Please indicate your net (after tax) monthly income

- Under 500 €
- 500 € – 1000 €
- 1000 € – 3000 €
- 3000 € – 6000 €
- 6000 € – 10000 €
- Over 10000 €
- Prefer not to say

End page

Thank you for your time and participation! Your contribution is highly valued!

Appendix 2. The summary of all hypothesis and theories tested for identification of social impact.

Table 1. Dependent and independent variables and assumed causal inference of the study.

Variables							
<i>Independent:</i> Initiatives':				<i>Dependent:</i>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online publications; • Workshops, events, tutorials; • Email newsletters; • Closing loops activity. 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raised public awareness about food and/or plastic waste • Increased involvement in the activity of the initiatives • Behavioral change towards more conscious lifestyle 			
Causal inference							
<i>Null Hypothesis (H0):</i> There is no correlation between initiatives' in investigation actions and public awareness, involvement and behavioral change.	<i>Hypothesis H1:</i> There is a correlation between initiatives' in investigation actions and public awareness, involvement and behavioral change.	<i>Hypothesis H2:</i> There is a correlation between initiatives' in investigation actions and public awareness and involvement but there is no significant influence on behavioral change.	<i>Hypothesis H3:</i> There is a correlation between initiatives' in investigation actions and public awareness and behavioral change but there is no significant impact on public involvement.	<i>Hypothesis H4:</i> There is a correlation between initiatives' in investigation actions and public awareness but there is no significant impact on public involvement and behavioral change.	<i>Hypothesis H5:</i> There is a correlation between initiatives' in investigation actions and public involvement and behavioral change but there is no significant influence on public awareness.	<i>Hypothesis H6:</i> There is a correlation between initiatives' in investigation actions and public involvement but there is no significant influence on public awareness and behavioral change.	<i>Hypothesis H7:</i> There is a correlation between initiatives' in investigation actions and behavioral change but there is no significant influence on public awareness and involvement.
Theory 0: The circular bottom-up initiatives have no significant influence on the social dimension in Amsterdam's transition towards circularity having no significant	Theory 1: The circular bottom-up initiatives positively affect the social dimension in Amsterdam's transition towards circularity increasing public	Theory 2: The circular bottom-up initiatives positively affect the social dimension in Amsterdam's transition towards circularity increasing public	Theory 3: The circular bottom-up initiatives positively affect the social dimension in Amsterdam's transition towards circularity increasing public	Theory 4: The circular bottom-up initiatives have a limited effect on the social dimension in Amsterdam's transition towards circularity increasing	Theory 5: The circular bottom-up initiatives positively affect the social dimension in Amsterdam's transition towards circularity increasing public	Theory 6: The circular bottom-up initiatives have a limited effect on the social dimension in Amsterdam's transition towards circularity increasing	Theory 7: The circular bottom-up initiatives have a limited effect on the social dimension in Amsterdam's transition towards circularity contributing

effect on public awareness and involvement and behavioral change towards more conscious lifestyle.	awareness and involvement and contributing to behavioral change towards more conscious lifestyle.	awareness and involvement but having no significant impact on behavioral change towards more conscious lifestyle.	awareness and stimulating behavioral change towards more conscious lifestyle but having no significant impact on public involvement.	public awareness but having no significant impact on public involvement and behavioral change towards more conscious lifestyle.	involvement and contributing to behavioral change towards more conscious lifestyle but having no significant impact on public awareness.	public involvement but having no significant impact on behavioral change towards more conscious lifestyle and public awareness.	to behavioral change towards more conscious lifestyle but having no significant impact on public awareness and involvement.
--	---	---	--	---	--	---	---

Results

The circular bottom-up initiatives succeed to exert positive influence on the public involvement. However, according to the data analysis, the awareness of the community involved in the activities of these BUIs is not statistically different from the awareness of those who do not take part in such activities. The findings concerning the behavioral change are ambiguous since the most respondents from the study group acknowledge the positive impact of the BUIs on their behavioral patterns, however, the statistical analysis does not show the same result.

Conclusion

Null Hypothesis (H0) and Theory 0 are rejected	Hypothesis H1 and Theory 1 are rejected	Hypothesis H2 and Theory 2 are rejected	Hypothesis H3 and Theory 3 are rejected	Hypothesis H4 and Theory 4 are rejected	Hypothesis H5 and Theory 5 are accepted	Hypothesis H6 and Theory 6 are accepted	Hypothesis H7 and Theory 7 are rejected
---	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Appendix 3. The summary of the process of the content analysis conduction

Table 2. Step-by-step process of a content analysis conduction.

1. Identification of units	Words or phrases;
2. Purposive source sampling	<p>Information source:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refers to the activity of the examined initiatives; • Describes the economic and environmental effect of such activity; • Was published after 2015. <p>The maximum possible number of sources is examined considering the set time frames (two-three weeks);</p>
3.1. Codebook creation	<p>Codebook creation is mostly theory-driven, i.e. deductive. Steps of this process are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Theme identification; • Category identification; • Code creation (Elo & Kyngäs, 2008). <p>The steps of inductive, i.e. data-driven analysis are reversed, they start with the code creating and finish with theme identification;</p>
3.2. Pre-testing of the codebook	Manual coding of one A4 page to check for a coding consistency;
4. Data codification	Manual coding of all relevant information sources;
5. Coded data analysis	Interpretation of the coded material and generalization of the results.

Appendix 4. Extended operationalization of variables for analysis

Table 3. Operationalization of the variables.

Type of impact	Relevant perspective	Category of measure	Unit of measure proposed in the literature	Unit of measure in this research
Environmental impact	Closing loops	Food waste reduction	Kg of waste being upcycled per week/month/year (Martínez, 2016); amount of resources saved (kg/day) (Marin et al., 2018); amount of reused resources (Owen & Liddell, 2016); Amount of food waste treated (%/total food waste) (Ferreira & Fuso-Nerini, 2019).	Saved food (kg/year)
			Amount (%) of GHG reduction (Crocì, 2018)	Quantity GHG avoided (kgCO ₂ eq/year)
	Resource cooperation (input)	Plastic waste reduction	Amount of resources saved (Marin et al., 2018); amount of recycled resources (Owen & Liddell, 2016)	Gathered plastic (kg/year)
				Number of PET-bottles collected (per year)
Economic impact	Closing loops	Value maximization	Revenue from recycled goods sold (€/month) (Eurocities, 2017); potential value of the material after reuse (€) (ibid.)	(Market) price of the goods (€)
	Resource cooperation (input)			Price of otherwise to be wasted food or plastic (€)
	Resource cooperation (finance)	Funding	Amount received from partners (Martínez, 2016)	Not examined in this study
Social impact	Resource cooperation (media)	Appearance in media	Number of times promotional video has been watched (Martínez, 2016)	Not examined in this study
	Community	Inclusiveness	Social diversity of the projects (Martínez, 2016)	Not examined in this study
		Involvement	Number of actively participating people (Ferreira & Fuso-Nerini, 2019; Martínez, 2016)	In this study, not measured in units
			Number of jobs created (Crocì, 2018; Eurocities, 2017; Marin et al., 2018)	Not examined in this study
	Awareness and behavioral change	Raised awareness	Number of people attending events (Martínez, 2016)	In this study, not measured in units
		Eco-habits adoption	Number of people who have changed their habits (Martínez, 2016)	In this study, not measured in units

Other	Resource cooperation (knowledge)	Knowledge transfer	Number of meetings established for educational purposes (Martínez, 2016); Number of internal events and dissemination activities about CE (Eurocities, 2017)	Presence of the corresponding codes such as “involving actors”
	Transition	Regime change	-	Presence of the corresponding codes such as “worldwide”, “internationally”
Commitment to circularity	Mission	Mission statement	Aspiration to preserve the environment, enhance the economic activity while actively including the local community must be included the mission statement (Martínez, 2016)	Quantity of environmental, economic, social and other impact codes

Appendix 5. SPSS output for the age and income responses.

The following Figure 5 and Figure 6 represent the distribution of age and income of the respondents accordingly. Both figures are skewed to the right.

Figure 5. Age of the respondents.

Figure 6. Income of the respondents.

Appendix 6. Codebooks for the content analysis of the mission statements.

Table 13. Content analysis of TBYW's mission statement.

Taste Before You Waste			
Theme	Category (Perspective)	Code	Mission statement
Environmental impact	Closing loops	Reduce consumer food waste	“Taste Before You Waste is a foundation with the mission to reduce consumer food waste by providing citizens with the inspiration, knowledge and opportunity for responsible and waste-free consumption. We create a welcoming community of foodies from all over the world by hosting donation-based events such as Food Cycle Markets, Wasteless Dinners, Educational Workshops, Event Caterings and Presentations, showcasing that the food which is currently regarded as waste is actually delicious and valuable.
Economic impact	Resource Cooperation (input)		
Social impact	Awareness and behavioral change	Providing with [...] opportunity for responsible and waste-free consumption	Taste Before You Waste has been popping up all over the Netherlands, in Bussum, Utrecht, The Hague and internationally in Kingston, Canada and Auckland New Zealand! Serving consciousness on a platter is how the Foundation wants to revolutionise the food system, one neighbourhood at a time.” (TBYW, 2019 – b, p. 8).
		Showcasing that the food [...] regarded as waste is [...] valuable	
		Providing [...] with the inspiration, knowledge	
	Community	Citizens	
Transition	Regime change	Community	
		Hosting [...] events	
		All over the world	
		Internationally	
		Wants to revolutionise the food system	

Table 14. Content analysis of InStock Restaurant's mission statement.

InStock Restaurant			
Theme	Theme (Perspective)	Code	Mission statement
	Closing loops	Food is wasted	

Environmental impact Economic impact	Resource Cooperation (input)	Reduce food waste	<p>“One third of the food in our world is wasted. Our mission is to reduce food waste and create awareness of the issue. We take on this challenge quite literally by using products that would otherwise remain unsold. Moreover, we believe that awareness should be raised in a positive and fun way. Food is all about enjoyment after all! We have noticed that we’ve gotten more out of touch with the food we eat in the last decades. With all the facilities that the present-day has to offer, we don’t need to put much effort into our meals anymore. There’s enough food and plenty of choice. Our goal is to make people value food more in several ways: through a good dining experience in one of our restaurants, via our masterclasses, and by selling products like our cook books InStock Cooking and Circular Chefs and our craft beers Pieper Bier and Bammetjes Bier.” (InStock Restaurant, n.d.)</p>
		Using products that [...] remain unsold	
		Gotten more out of touch with the food	
Social Impact	Awareness and behavioral change	Create awareness	
		Awareness should be raised	
		Selling products like [...] cook books [...] and [...] craft beers	
	Community	Good dining experience	
Awareness and behavioral change	Masterclasses		
Community			

Table 15. Content analysis of Plastic Whale’s mission statement.

Plastic Whale			
Theme	Theme (Perspective)	Code	Mission statement
Environmental impact	Closing loops	Plastic-free waters	<p>“Plastic Whale is a social enterprise with a mission - we want plastic-free waters. Worldwide. We achieve this by showing others that economic value can be created from plastic waste, involving as many people and businesses as possible within the pillars:</p>
		We collect	
Economic impact	Resource Cooperation (input)	We Create	
		Showing others that economic value can be created from plastic waste	
Social Impact			

	Awareness and behavioral change	We educate	"We Collect, We Create, We Educate." (Plastic Whale, n.d.).
	Community	Social	
		Involving as many people as possible	
Transition	Regime change	Worldwide	
Other	Resource Cooperation (knowledge)	Involving as many businesses as possible	

Table 16. Content analysis of WASTEDlab's mission statement.

WASTEDlab			
Theme	Theme (Perspective)	Code	Mission statement
Environmental impact	Closing loops	Giving new value to plastic waste	"WASTED is a multi-faceted initiative aiming to integrate local community members and actors in giving new value to plastic waste. Initiated by CITIES Foundation, the project's initial pilot took place in Amsterdam Noord, running January through August 2015. The pilot centralized around a combination of three activities: 1) localized reprocessing of plastic waste into new, useful products; 2) a community-activated recycling and reward system; and 3) an educational program for local secondary schools. In addition to these central project elements, we organized a Summer Program to further involve citizens
Economic impact		Resource Cooperation (input)	
	Material design		
	Material (re)use and product design		
Social impact	Awareness and behavioral change	An education program for local secondary school	
		Raise awareness	
	Community	Integrate local community	
		A community-activated recycling and reward system	

		Involve citizens	and raise awareness . Through these activities, WASTED became a dual engine of social and material design , where the social benefits of local neighborhood activation coincided with and enforced the aim of setting new, sustainable standards for material (re)use and product design .” (CITIES Foundation, 2015, p.1).
		Social design	
		Social benefits	
Other	Resource Cooperation (knowledge)	Integrate actors	